

Fast Modeling of ABL-Wind Farm Interactions with Atmospheric Stability

Author:
Severijn D'hoedt

DTU Wind-M-0768
June, 2025

Author:
Severijn D'hoedt

Title:
Fast Modeling of ABL-Wind Farm Interactions with Atmospheric Stability

DTU Wind-M-0768
June, 2025

ECTS: 30

Education: European Wind Energy Master
- Wind Farms and Atmospheric Physics

Supervisors:

Alexander Meyer Forsting
DTU Wind & Energy Systems

Elliot Simon
DTU Wind & Energy Systems

Martin Kühn
ForWind - Oldenburg University

Gerald Steinfeld
ForWind - Oldenburg University

Remarks:

This report is submitted as partial fulfillment of the requirements for graduation in the above education at the Technical University of Denmark

DTU Wind & Energy Systems is a department of the Technical University of Denmark with a unique integration of research, education, innovation and public/private sector consulting in the field of wind energy. Our activities develop new opportunities and technology for the global and Danish exploitation of wind energy. Research focuses on key technical-scientific fields, which are central for the development, innovation and use of wind energy and provides the basis for advanced education at the education.

Technical University of Denmark Department of Wind Energy
Frederiksborgvej 399
4000 Roskilde
Denmark
www.wind.dtu.dk

Fast Modeling of ABL-Wind Farm Interactions with Atmospheric Stability
Towards More Reliable Power Forecasting with Coupled Wake-ABL Dynamics
and Atmospheric Stability

Master Thesis

June, 2025

By

Severijn D'hoedt

Copyright: Reproduction of this publication in whole or in part must include
the customary bibliographic citation, including author attribution,
report title, etc.

Cover photo: Vibeke Hempler, 2012

Published by: DTU, Department of Wind and Energy Systems, Frederiksborgvej
399, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark Denmark
<https://wind.dtu.dk/>

ISSN: [0000-0000] (electronic version)

ISBN: [000-00-0000-000-0] (electronic version)

ISSN: [0000-0000] (printed version)

ISBN: [000-00-0000-000-0] (printed version)

Approval

This thesis was conducted over six months at the *Department for DTU Wind & Energy Systems*, at the *Technical University of Denmark*, in collaboration with *Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg (UOL)*. It is submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the *European Wind Energy Master (EWEM)* degree within the *Wind Farms and Atmospheric Physics* track. A basic understanding of *fluid dynamics* is assumed for the reader.

Severijn D'hoedt - s234022

Severijn D'hoedt

Signature

03/07/2025

Date

Abstract

Standard wake models used in wind energy assessments often neglect the role of the background atmospheric state, assuming horizontally uniform inflow and neutral conditions. This simplification limits their ability to predict flow adjustments such as upstream deceleration and internal pressure gradients that arise from wind farm–atmosphere interactions. To address this, this thesis evaluates DTU’s in-house Multi-Scale Coupled (MSC) model, which takes into account mesoscale-informed atmospheric inputs into a fast, engineering-oriented framework. The model couples micro-scale wake effects with a three-layer representation of the atmospheric boundary layer, allowing it to respond to the simplified state of the background flow. Validation is performed using high-resolution SCADA, meteorological (lidar and met mast), and mesoscale data from the Amrumbank West wind farm, selected for its uniform layout and dense instrumentation as part of the GLOBE campaign. The analysis focuses on well-mixed, conventionally neutral boundary layer conditions, filtered using potential temperature gradients and wind direction to isolate the effects of ABL height and atmospheric stratification. The MSC model was benchmarked against two PyWake reference models. While differences were minimal under deep, well-mixed ABLs, substantial deviations emerged under shallow-layer conditions. These were not spatially uniform: the MSC model consistently predicted lower front-row power and stronger downstream recovery, reflecting the global blockage pattern. The magnitude of these effects increased with decreasing ABL height. Further analysis linked this behavior to the Froude number regime. Although subcritical and supercritical flows showed different trends, deviations were present across the full range. Under near-neutral, subcritical conditions, pressure perturbations correlated well with ABL height. In more stratified ABLs, often associated with higher Froude numbers, pressure build-up became more variable, yet remained elevated in several cases, suggesting a growing role of internal gravity waves where interfacial wave effects diminish. Overall, wind farm–atmosphere interactions are shaped by a dynamic balance between internal and interfacial gravity wave mechanisms, governed by ABL height, stratification, and flow regime. These findings indicate that the Froude number alone may not fully capture the complexity of mesoscale–farm coupling.

Acknowledgements

Filled with a profound sense of gratitude, I present to you my Master's thesis as the milestone of this unforgettable two-year academic journey. Starting the European Wind Energy Master (EWEM) in Wind Farms and Atmospheric Physics between DTU and UOL marked the beginning of an incredible experience, both academically and personally. It has been truly enriching to engage with so many passionate and skilled people, whose expertise and willingness to share their knowledge have been deeply inspiring and invaluable to my growth.

I have always been fascinated by engineering and atmospheric processes, and this thesis gave me the opportunity to work at the intersection of both, something I've long aspired to. It has been an immensely rewarding experience. However, I could never have accomplished this without the support of certain people, to whom I would like to express my deepest gratitude. Their guidance and encouragement at various stages of this journey have been essential in helping me reach this point.

First and foremost, I extend my sincere thanks to my supervisors Alexander Meyer Forsting (DTU) and Gerald Steinfeld (UOL) for their continuous support, insightful feedback, and constructive discussions throughout this thesis. Their guidance was invaluable in shaping both the technical content and the broader perspective of this work. A special thank you goes to Alexander for his time in guiding me through the newest in-house multi-scale coupling (MSC) code, which formed the foundation of this study. I would also like to thank Elliot Simon for his support in working with the GLOBE dataset—granting access and helping me navigate its structure and use. It has truly been a privilege to work with such a high-quality dataset. I am also grateful to the data operations teams at DTU for providing the meteorological data.

Usage rights for the data used in this study were granted via the consortium agreement between DTU and the Offshore Wind Accelerator (OWA) Global Blockage Experiment (GLOBE). I would like to sincerely thank the project partners for enabling access to these valuable datasets, including the Carbon Trust, RWE, ScottishPower Renewables, Shell, SSE Renewables, TotalEnergies, and Vattenfall. The SCADA data used in this study was made available through their contributions. The WRF data and ABL height measurements were provided by Fraunhofer IWES via the X-Wakes project. I gratefully acknowledge the financial support from the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK) for funding this the X-Wakes project.

Last but not least, I would like to extend a heartfelt thank you to some of the most important people in my life. First, to my parents, Jeroen and Ingrid, and my family, for giving me the opportunity to pursue my studies abroad and for their continued support from Belgium. Their constant encouragement and belief in me have meant the world, and for that, I am truly grateful. A heartfelt thank you also goes to my girlfriend Marta for her unwavering support throughout this journey, for always being there to help me out and offer advice and encouragement whenever

I needed it.

So to all of you, thank you!

Severijn D'hoedt

Copenhagen, June 27, 2025

Contents

Preface	ii
Abstract	iii
Acknowledgements	iv
1 Introduction	1
2 Literature Review	4
2.1 Structure and Stability of the Atmospheric Boundary Layer	4
2.1.1 The Atmospheric Boundary Layer	5
2.1.2 Definition and Classification of Atmospheric Stability	6
2.1.3 Governing Parameters and Stability Metrics	9
2.2 Characterizing the Atmospheric Background State	10
2.2.1 The diurnal ABL cycle	11
2.2.2 CBL-Characterization in Maritime Climates	13
2.2.3 Modeling the Vertical Temperature Profiles of a CBL	14
2.2.4 Rampanelli Fitting Algorithm	16
2.3 Micro-Scale Effects in Wind Farms	20
2.3.1 Definition and Scope	20
2.3.2 Existing Micro-Scale Wake Models	21
2.3.3 Wake Superposition Methods	27
2.4 Meso-Scale Effects Induced by Wind Farms	29
2.4.1 Global Wind Farm Blockage and Pressure Effects	29
2.4.2 The generation of Gravity Waves by Wind Farm	31
2.4.3 Flow Adaptation and Recovery at the Meso-Scale	32
2.4.4 The Importance of Accounting for meso-scale effects in Flow Modeling	33
2.5 Coupled Micro–Meso Scale Modeling	34
2.5.1 The Need for Coupling in Wind Farm Modeling	34
2.5.2 Existing Coupled Modeling Approaches	34
2.5.3 The Multi-Scale Coupled Model	36
3 Study Area and Data Description	41
3.1 Wind Farm Cluster Layout and Wind Turbine types	41
3.2 Data Sources	43
4 Convective Boundary Layer Filtering	47
4.1 CBL-Conditions	47
4.1.1 Stability Filter	47
4.1.2 Potential Temperature Difference (PTD) Filter	50
4.2 Statistical Analysis of Filtered CBL Cases	53
5 Rampanelli Potential Temperature Profile Fitting	56
5.1 Implementation approach	56
5.2 Fitting Results	57

6	Power Modeling Methodology	65
6.1	PyWake Micro-Scale Models	65
6.2	Micro-Scale Power Model Choice and Case Study Inputs	67
6.3	Multi-Scale Coupling Model	68
7	Simulation Configuration	71
7.1	Case Study Description	71
7.2	Final Case Selection	71
7.3	Model Configuration and Inputs	76
7.4	Wake Model Tuning	78
8	Results & Discussion	81
8.1	Atmospheric Stability Characterization	81
8.1.1	The Froude Number	81
8.1.2	Brunt–Väisälä Frequency N	82
8.2	Microscale Model Performance Across Atmospheric Conditions	83
8.2.1	Overall Power Prediction Accuracy	83
8.2.2	Impact of ABL Height on Power Prediction	86
8.2.3	Model Performance in Relation to Froude Number	89
8.3	The Role of ABL Height in Modulating Mesoscale–Wind Farm Interactions	94
9	Conclusion	98
10	Limitations & Future Work	100

1 Introduction

Denmark has played an important role in shaping today's wind energy sector, profiling itself as a pioneer in wind power technology and offshore wind farm development. Wind farms, both onshore and offshore, have therefore been critical in keeping the country on track to meet its renewable energy targets in terms of commitments to the Paris Agreement for 2030 and beyond [1, 2]. Today, wind power accounts for roughly 53.4% of the electricity supply in Denmark, yet the country continues to push on with the deployment of offshore wind to maintain the climate targets it has set [1].

Over the past decade, the North Sea has seen substantial growth in offshore wind energy, with installed capacity exceeding 25 gigawatts (GW) as of 2025 [3]. This expansion is expected to accelerate, with planned capacity rising to 120 GW by 2030 and 300 GW by 2050. Denmark is actively contributing to this growth with large-scale projects such as the Thor Offshore Wind Farm, set to add over 1 GW to the grid upon completion in 2027, making it the country's largest offshore wind project to date [4]. Additionally, the Energy Island North Sea, an artificial island planned 80 km west of Jutland, is expected to support 3 GW of offshore wind in its initial phase, with potential expansion up to 10 GW by 2036 [2].

Despite these ambitious developments, the rapid growth in both the number and size of wind energy projects has exposed critical structural limitations in the current approach to wind farm siting and power forecasting [3]. Modern wind turbines, now exceeding 260 meters in height with capacities of up to 16 MW per turbine, introduce new aerodynamic and atmospheric challenges, particularly regarding wake interactions and large-scale atmospheric effects, as well as the variation of wind direction with height (wind veer), which becomes increasingly relevant at these scales [5].

Accurately predicting wind farm power output is essential for both short-term and long-term energy planning. In the short term, high-resolution power forecasts are critical for maintaining grid stability and enabling efficient integration of variable renewables, especially as the energy system becomes increasingly reliant on wind and solar power. In the long term, improving the accuracy of power production and AEP estimates directly reduces uncertainty in project performance, leading to more reliable projections of the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE). This not only makes wind projects economically more feasible, but also helps establish them as a more reliable option in the shift to a low-carbon energy system. To achieve all this, there is a need for reliable and accurate power prediction models.

Conventional models often fail to capture the full complexity of interactions between large wind farms and the atmospheric boundary layer. Under certain conditions, wind farms vertically displace the boundary layer, triggering atmospheric gravity waves that induce horizontal pressure gradients and modify the flow at turbine locations, ultimately impacting power production. This potentially can also cause an upstream blockage region that reduces the available wind resource be-

fore reaching the first turbine row [5]. While traditional models focused primarily on downstream wake effects, the introduction of blockage models, and more recently, global blockage, has revealed that wind farms can induce significant flow changes both upstream and downstream on much larger spatial scales. Figure 1 visualizes the spatial scales relevant to wind power, from large-scale atmospheric dynamics to turbine-scale turbulence. Capturing these large-scale atmospheric effects is crucial not only for improving power output predictions but also for addressing the emerging challenge of accurately assessing wind resources within increasingly large wind farm clusters, an essential step toward meeting renewable energy targets in Denmark and across the North Sea region.

This thesis aims to validate a DTU in-house code that couples multi-scale atmospheric dynamics by applying it to the N4 Cluster of the German Bight, which consists of three wind farms, Amrumbank West, Nordsee Ost, and Meerwind, located off the German North Sea coast. Leveraging data from the GLOBE campaign, including measurements from met masts, scanning lidars, buoy-based lidars, ERA5 reanalysis, and WRF model outputs, the model can be initialized with realistic atmospheric inputs. Prior to model initialization, the dataset is filtered to include only convective and neutral boundary layer (C(N)BL) conditions to ensure consistency with model assumptions. For the coupled micro–meso-scale model, the Rampanelli potential temperature fitting algorithm is applied to extract key atmospheric parameters, such as inversion base height, temperature inversion strength, free atmospheric lapse rate, and atmospheric boundary layer height. Power forecasting is conducted using two micro-scale wake models and DTU’s multi-scale coupled (MSC) model. Simulated power outputs are benchmarked against SCADA data from the Amrumbank West wind farm to assess model accuracy under conventionally neutral boundary layer conditions. Special focus is placed on evaluating how atmospheric stability, captured through ABL height and Froude number, affects intra-farm power distribution.

The remainder of this thesis is structured as follows. Chapter 2 presents a literature review covering ABL structure, stability classification, and key micro- and meso-scale processes relevant to wind farm modeling, with emphasis on their coupling. Chapter 3 describes the study area and data sources, followed by Chapter 4, which details the filtering applied to isolate the study cases. Chapter 5 explains the fitting of vertical potential temperature profiles using the Rampanelli algorithm. Chapters 6 and 7 present the power modeling methodology and simulation setup. In Chapter 8, model results are analyzed with respect to ABL height and flow regime, showing how both ABL height and the stability of the ABL and free atmosphere influence intra-farm power distribution. Finally, a conclusion is presented, outlining key findings, current limitations, and directions for future research.

Figure 1: Spatial scales relevant to wind power, from large-scale atmospheric dynamics to turbine-scale turbulence. Image reproduced from Sempreviva et al. (2019) [6].

2 Literature Review

This literature review provides an overview of research relevant to the current study, structured into five main sections.

The first section introduces the structure and dynamics of the ABL, with particular focus on atmospheric stability and the classification of ABL regimes into convective boundary layers (CBL), stable boundary layers (SBL), and neutral residual layers (NRL), with special emphasis on the CBL regime, which is central to this study. In this context, vertical profiles of atmospheric variables, especially the potential temperature profile, are introduced, as they form the basis for stability classification. Particular attention is given to the Rampanelli fitting method, which enables the identification of key ABL parameters in a physically consistent manner, providing a robust framework for distinguishing between convective, stable, and residual boundary layers.

The second section describes methods for characterizing the atmospheric background state, including the diurnal evolution of the ABL and the influence of maritime conditions on CBL development. This section also outlines how vertical profiles of temperature are modeled and fitted, with a focus on the Rampanelli algorithm used for stratification parameterization.

The third section reviews microscale wake models, focusing on their formulation, assumptions, and limitations, as well as their adaptability to site-specific conditions. Emphasis is placed on strategies for model tuning and optimization, and on the various wake superposition methods used to represent turbine interactions within a wind farm.

The fourth section shifts to mesoscale flow effects, covering the concepts of global wind farm blockage, pressure gradients, and the generation of atmospheric gravity waves by large wind farms. These mesoscale phenomena are shown to potentially modify upstream inflow and downstream recovery, thereby affecting turbine performance in ways not captured by traditional microscale models.

Finally, the fifth section presents coupled micro-mesoscale modeling approaches, highlighting the importance of integrating microscale wake effects with mesoscale atmospheric processes for accurate power prediction. Existing coupling strategies are reviewed, with particular attention to the MSC model proposed by Stipa et al. [5], which aligns closely with the in-house model applied in this thesis.

2.1 Structure and Stability of the Atmospheric Boundary Layer

This subsection provides a detailed explanation of the structure of the ABL and its diurnal cycle. It introduces the concept of atmospheric stability, beginning with the definition of potential temperature and progressing toward commonly used stability metrics such as the Monin-Obukhov length L and the bulk Richardson number Ri_b .

2.1.1 The Atmospheric Boundary Layer

The Earth's surface acts as the boundary of the atmospheric domain, with its lowest part known as the troposphere, extending up to 11 km in height. The lowest section of the troposphere is directly influenced by the Earth's surface, forming the ABL. The remaining part of the troposphere in which the air is unaffected by the Earth's surface is called the free atmosphere. The ABL evolves under the influence of multiple forcings resulting in spatial and temporal variability in its structure. This results in a diurnal cycle that is highly sensitive to weather conditions and the atmospheric state at any given time and location. Consequently, its thickness fluctuates significantly, ranging from a few hundred meters to several kilometers.

One of the key factors shaping the ABL is wind, which governs the transport of heat, moisture, momentum, and pollutants. Airflow can be divided into mean wind, turbulence, and waves, which can exist separately or together. In the boundary layer, horizontal transport is mainly driven by the mean wind, while turbulence dominates vertical mixing. As the ground warms and cools in response to solar radiation, turbulence facilitates the transport of scalars such as heat, temperature, and humidity in the vertical direction, shaping the atmospheric boundary layer. Waves transport fewer scalars but are more essential in transferring momentum and energy. They are triggered by mean-wind shear and by obstacles in the mean flow, e.g., a wind farm.

A common method for analyzing atmospheric flows is to apply Reynolds decomposition, separating variables into mean and perturbation components to distinguish between steady and fluctuating behaviors. This thesis develops a fast ABL–wind farm interaction model that includes large-scale wave effects, such as gravity waves, which are important for modulating wind farm flow. While the model captures wave-induced dynamics, it does not resolve large-scale turbulent mixing. Unlike turbulence, characterized by chaotic, multi-scale energy transfer, gravity waves are coherent motions typically found in more laminar conditions. In contrast, wake models (e.g. the `PyWake` models used in this thesis) focus on micro-scale turbulence effects, modeling wake deficits and recovery using parametrized turbulence intensities. The combined influence of turbulence, wave dynamics, and mesoscale ABL structure on wind farm performance is explored in detail in later sections.

The following subsection introduces the concept of atmospheric stability, including its definition, classification, and the governing parameters and stability metrics used for its quantification. This is of major importance for the remainder of this thesis, as it enables the quantification of stability effects on wind, turbulent kinetic energy, and temperature profiles, which directly influence wind farm performance.

2.1.2 Definition and Classification of Atmospheric Stability

The previous paragraph discussed how the atmospheric boundary layer evolves in response to surface forcing, varying in time and space. The extent to which the ABL responds to these surface forcings is strongly determined by the degree of atmospheric stability. Atmospheric stability can be defined as the resistance of the atmosphere to vertical motion and mixing. As a consequence, the state of stability determines the vertical distribution of turbulence and the transport of momentum, heat, and other scalars. Atmospheric stability is directly related to the temperature structure of the ABL, with potential temperature (θ) being the primary metric used to quantify it. The potential temperature represents the temperature a parcel of air would attain if it were brought adiabatically to the surface, accounting for the heating it undergoes due to compression during descent. The variation of this parameter with height defines the stability characteristics of the atmosphere. As this parameter is of great importance in this work, a detailed derivation of the potential temperature, along with its physical interpretation and its role in atmospheric stability characterization, is presented below.

Derivation of the potential temperature parameter

This paragraph derives the formulation of the potential temperature variable θ . The derivation starts with formulating the first law of thermodynamics for an air parcel as in Equation (1). In this expression variable dq represent the external heat change, c_p the specific heat capacity at constant pressure, dT the temperature change, ρ the air density and dp the change in pressure.

$$dq = c_p dT - \frac{1}{\rho} dp \quad (1)$$

Since an air parcel undergoes adiabatic vertical motion, the heat exchange term (dq) is set to zero, as there is no heat transfer with the surroundings. Consequently, Equation (1) simplifies to Equation (2). Next, the ideal gas law for dry air, Equation (3), is substituted into Equation (2) with R the specific gas constant for dry air.

$$c_p dT = \frac{1}{\rho} dp \quad (2)$$

$$p = \rho RT \quad (3)$$

The adiabatic equation, after the above substitution and rearrangement of terms, is given by Equation (4). The expression is then integrated on both sides, i.e., a temperature integration from the initial temperature T to the potential temperature θ , and a pressure integration from the initial pressure p to the reference pressure p_0 , as shown in Equation (5). Evaluating the integral and rearranging the terms results in Equation (6), which defines the potential temperature as a function of height z , where $T(z) = T_0 - \Gamma_d z$. Here, Γ_d represents the dry adiabatic lapse rate, defined as the negative ratio of temperature change with respect to height change, and is given by $\Gamma_d = 0.0098 \text{ K m}^{-1}$.

$$\frac{dT}{T} = \frac{R}{c_p} \frac{dp}{p} \quad (4)$$

$$\int_T^\theta \frac{dT}{T} = \frac{R}{c_p} \int_p^{p_0} \frac{dp}{p} \quad (5)$$

$$\theta(z) = T(z) \left(\frac{p_0}{p} \right)^{R/c_p} \quad (6)$$

Static Stability and Brunt-Väisälä Frequency

As mentioned before, static stability describes the resistance of the atmosphere to vertical motion. This vertical motion is driven by the buoyancy force, which arises due to the density difference between an air parcel and its surroundings. An atmosphere that restores the position of a displaced air parcel—whether it moves upward or downward—back to its original position is termed statically stable. Conversely, if the air parcel experiences no restoring force and continues to move away from its initial position, the atmosphere is statically unstable. This behavior is directly linked to the vertical gradient of the previously derived parameter, the potential temperature θ .

According to Archimedes' principle, the buoyancy force, or the force per unit mass due to density differences with the surroundings, is given by Equation (7), where ρ and ρ' represent the ambient and parcel densities, respectively. The variable g denotes the gravitational acceleration. By applying the ideal gas law and the definition of potential temperature, the density perturbation can be expressed as shown in Equation (8), i.e., as a function of the difference in potential temperature between the air parcel, θ' , and the background θ .

$$F = g \frac{\rho' - \rho}{\rho} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d^2 z}{dt^2} = g \left(\frac{\theta' - \theta}{\theta} \right) \quad (8)$$

For relatively small displacements, it can be assumed that the potential temperature varies linearly with height, such that the air parcel's temperature θ' at height z' can be written as:

$$\theta' = \theta + z' \frac{d\theta}{dz}$$

Substituting this into Equation (8) results in Equation (9). The variable N in the this expression is known as the Brunt-Väisälä frequency and is defined by Equation (10) is thus directly related with the gradient of the potential temperature with height. The sign of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency (and consequently the sign of the potential temperature gradient) determines the stability of the atmosphere.

$$\frac{d^2 z'}{dt^2} = -N^2 z' \quad (9)$$

$$N^2 = \frac{g}{\theta} \frac{d\theta}{dz} \quad (10)$$

For $N^2 > 0$, the displacement of the air parcel is limited around its equilibrium position. The suppression of vertical motion results in an atmosphere characterized by weak levels of turbulence. The atmosphere is statically stable, as the potential temperature increases with height ($\frac{d\theta}{dz} > 0$). When an air parcel is displaced upward, it enters a warmer environment, making it denser than the surrounding air and causing it to sink back to its original position. Conversely, if displaced downward, it moves into a cooler environment, becomes less dense than its surroundings, and rises back to its initial position.

For cases in which $N^2 < 0$, the atmosphere is statically unstable, driving strong turbulence as the potential temperature decreases with height ($\frac{d\theta}{dz} < 0$). In an unstable situation, a rising air parcel moves into a warmer environment, making it less dense than its surroundings and continuing to rise. Similarly, a descending air parcel encounters cooler air, becoming denser and thus continuing to sink. This process leads to sustained vertical motion, enhancing turbulence and mixing.

An atmosphere for which $N^2 = 0$ is called a neutrally stratified atmosphere. In this case, there is no restoring force as in stable conditions, meaning that an air parcel displaced vertically continues its motion without damping, amplification, or oscillation. A neutral atmosphere typically occurs when the potential temperature remains constant with height ($\frac{d\theta}{dz} = 0$).

Figure 2 visualizes the above concept of stability. The vertical line represent the neutral case, i.e., no change of the potential temperature θ with height. The negative ($\frac{d\theta}{dz} < 0$) and positive ($\frac{d\theta}{dz} > 0$) slope represent an unstable and stable atmosphere, respectively. [7].

Figure 2: Potential Temperature Gradient for Different Stability Regimes.

2.1.3 Governing Parameters and Stability Metrics

Several metrics are commonly used to quantify atmospheric stability, including the Obukhov length (L), the Richardson number (Ri), and the Bulk Richardson number (Ri_b). These parameters describe the balance between buoyancy forces and turbulence generation, providing insight into the role of atmospheric stability in energy dissipation, wind flow, and related processes. The following paragraphs give a brief introduction of these parameters, including their mathematical formulation and physical interpretation.

The Obukhov Length (L)

One of the most fundamental scaling parameters in boundary-layer meteorology is the Obukhov length L , which defines the height at which an equilibrium is found between buoyancy forces and generated turbulence, i.e., the height where turbulence is generated more by buoyancy than by wind shear. The expression for the Obukhov length L is given by Equation (11), with u_* representing the friction velocity, θ the previously introduced mean potential temperature, $\kappa = 0.41$ the von Kármán constant, $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$ the gravitational acceleration, and $\overline{w'\theta'}$ the turbulent heat flux, describing the transport of heat by turbulent structures [7].

$$L = -\frac{u_*^3 \theta}{\kappa g (\overline{w'\theta'})} \quad (11)$$

The stability regime is determined by the sign and magnitude of the Monin–Obukhov length L : positive L corresponds to stable conditions, negative L indicates unstable (convective) conditions, and as the surface heat flux approaches zero, L tends toward infinity, corresponding to neutral stability. A positive Obukhov length L signifies the suppression of turbulence by buoyancy forces, resulting in weak vertical mixing. Conversely, negative Obukhov lengths represent an atmosphere dominated by convective turbulence and strong mixing. For extremely high values of the Obukhov length, neutral conditions prevail. Further distinction between different levels of stability and instability is based on the magnitude of L and is listed in Table 1. Generally, a small $|L|$ corresponds to an atmosphere with strong stability effects, whereas large values indicate weak stratification.

Table 1: Stability classes according to classification by Pena et al. [8]

Obukhov length interval (m)	Atmospheric stability class
$10 \leq L \leq 50$	Very stable (vs)
$50 \leq L \leq 200$	Stable (s)
$200 \leq L \leq 500$	Near stable/neutral (ns)
$ L \geq 500$	Neutral (n)
$-500 \leq L \leq -200$	Near unstable/neutral (nu)
$-200 \leq L \leq -100$	Unstable (u)
$-100 \leq L \leq -50$	Very unstable (vu)

The Richardson Number Ri

Another key metric for defining stability is the dimensionless Richardson number Ri , which is determined by the mean temperature and wind speed. The expression for this bulk parameter is given by Equation (12) and represents the ratio of the virtual potential temperature gradient to the square of the vertical wind speed gradient, i.e., the wind shear, with an additional factor that includes gravitational acceleration g and potential temperature θ [7].

$$Ri = \frac{\frac{g}{\theta} \frac{d\theta_v}{dz}}{\left(\frac{du}{dz}\right)^2} \quad (12)$$

A Richardson number Ri greater than zero typically indicates stable conditions, where turbulence is suppressed by buoyancy. This corresponds to a positive vertical virtual potential temperature gradient $\frac{d\theta_v}{dz} > 0$ is introduced before. For unstable conditions, Ri is negative, where buoyancy contributes to turbulence and mixing. For Ri around 0, the atmosphere is neutral, where the production of turbulence is approximately in balance between suppression by buoyancy and production by shear [7].

As can be observed in the mathematical formulation of the Richardson number, Equation (12), local stability is determined by both the temperature gradient and wind shear. However, in many cases, particularly in offshore environments, high-frequency turbulence measurements are not available to directly evaluate these gradients. To address this limitation, the bulk Richardson number (Ri_b) is introduced, given by Equation (13). The subscripts 0 and z refer to the lower and upper height of the measurement, respectively. This metric relies on wind speed and temperature differences between two discrete heights, typically obtained from an offshore met mast or similar measurement infrastructure [9]. Since this stability metric varies with height, it is important to carefully select the height at which it is evaluated. This will be discussed in greater detail in the methodology section, where the evaluation heights for Ri_b are selected for the specific case study.

As will be elaborated in the next subsection, this formulation enables the derivation of the Obukhov length (L) for discrete measurements using Monin-Obukhov Similarity Theory (MOST). This allows for the assessment of stability effects on wind shear, wake recovery, turbulence intensity, and other key atmospheric processes relevant to wind energy applications.

$$Ri_b = \frac{\frac{g}{\theta_{v,0}} (\theta_{v,z} - \theta_{v,0}) z}{(u_z - u_0)^2} \quad (13)$$

2.2 Characterizing the Atmospheric Background State

The previous subsection introduced the structure of the ABL and the concept of atmospheric stability, including key stability metrics such as the Monin-Obukhov length and the Richardson number. While these metrics are valuable within the surface layer, their applicability becomes limited for flow problems involving the

entire ABL. To accurately capture the full vertical extent of the ABL, it is necessary to move beyond the surface layer and account for the characteristics of the entire boundary layer.

This subsection begins by discussing the diurnal evolution of the ABL and its variation across different terrains. It then introduces the Potential Temperature Difference (PTD) method, which is used to characterize the prevailing ABL regime. This method is particularly relevant to the present study, with a focus on CBL conditions, which are of primary interest due to their frequent occurrence in offshore environments. The well-mixed thermodynamic structure of CBLs offers a simplified framework for interpreting wake-ABL interactions. Furthermore, the relative insensitivity of CBLs to stability variations makes them a useful reference state for comparing microscale and multiscale wind farm modeling frameworks, as will be explored in later chapters.

Given the importance of the vertical potential temperature profile in defining the atmospheric background conditions for coupled models, this section concludes with an overview of various modeling approaches. Particular attention is paid to the Rampanelli fitting algorithm, which will serve as the foundational model for representing vertical potential temperature profiles throughout this thesis.

2.2.1 The diurnal ABL cycle

This section outlines how surface forcing acts as the primary mechanism driving the evolution of the ABL over time; refer to Section 2.1.1. This process is commonly referred to as the diurnal cycle of the ABL, denoting systematic changes in its structure over a 24-hour period. During the day, solar radiation heats the surface, while at night, radiative cooling dominates. In addition to the daily cycle, seasonal variations also play a crucial role in modulating ABL behavior by altering the magnitude and duration of surface energy exchange. In summer, extended daylight and higher solar input promote stronger surface warming and deeper boundary layer development. In contrast, wintertime brings reduced solar input, leading to cooler surfaces and shallower, more stable boundary layers.

Although diurnal changes in the ABL are observed globally, their manifestation varies significantly depending on the underlying surface type. Over land, the surface responds rapidly to radiative forcing due to its low heat capacity, leading to strong diurnal variability. In contrast, over oceanic surfaces, the high heat capacity of water dampens temperature fluctuations, resulting in a more gradual evolution of the ABL. Consequently, in offshore settings, such as the one considered in this study, diurnal effects are typically less pronounced, and boundary layer dynamics are more strongly governed by seasonal variability. Rather than showing a distinct day–night cycle, the marine ABL often evolves on longer time scales and is better characterized by shifts associated with seasonal forcing.

The onshore diurnal cycle is characterized by strong surface heating during the day, which increases the buoyancy of near-surface air parcels and initiates verti-

cal mixing. This mixing defines the CBL, which is typically well-mixed in potential temperature and moisture. Depending on the strength of the surface forcing, the CBL can grow from a few hundred meters to several kilometers in depth.

As the sun sets, the land surface cools rapidly, damping buoyancy-driven turbulence and promoting the formation of a SBL. In this regime, colder air accumulates near the ground, and turbulent mixing is suppressed. The SBL is usually much shallower than the CBL, typically extending only a few hundred meters. Above the SBL, the well-mixed air from the daytime CBL persists as a residual layer (RL), which remains relatively stratified and decoupled from the surface. As nighttime cooling continues, the SBL deepens, gradually taking over the RL from below. In the absence of turbulent mixing, wind shear decouples surface and upper-level flow, leading to calm conditions near the ground and stronger winds aloft. When surface heating resumes after sunrise, buoyancy-driven turbulence re-emerges and progressively breaks down the stable layer, mixing through the RL and forming a new convective boundary layer.

As mentioned above, this cycle behaves differently in marine conditions. Due to weaker surface heating and cooling, the diurnal evolution of the marine boundary layer (MBL) is damped. Day–night transitions in stability are often less distinct, and the MBL is more frequently characterized by near-neutral or weakly unstable conditions. Additionally, over the ocean, the stability is strongly influenced by the advection of air masses with different thermal characteristics. For instance, warm continental air advected over a cooler sea surface can induce stability, while cold air moving over warmer water promotes instability. Because air temperatures over land can change rapidly while the sea surface temperature adjusts much more slowly, the timescale of such advective processes becomes comparable to, or even dominates over, local heat fluxes when governing ABL stability offshore.

Figure 3 illustrates the vertical structure of the ABL as a function of time throughout the day, typically in onshore conditions. The time axis begins at noon, with a fully developed CBL driven by buoyant mixing. After sunset, surface cooling suppresses turbulence, and an SBL begins to form. The SBL, shown in black, continues to grow throughout the night until sunrise, when surface heating initiates the breakdown of the stable layer and the formation of a new convective boundary layer

Figure 3: Diurnal evolution of the atmospheric boundary layer, showing the development of a convective boundary layer (CBL) during the day and a stable boundary layer (SBL) at night with a residual layer (RL) aloft. Adapted from Stull (1988) [10].

The following subsection presents the methodology used to identify different ABL regimes, i.e., CBL, SBL, and NRL, with a particular focus on characterizing the CBL under maritime conditions, given the offshore location of the wind farm studied in this research.

2.2.2 CBL-Characterization in Maritime Climates

To understand the interaction between the atmosphere and the wind farm, it is essential to classify the structure of the ABL into distinct regimes. For this study, the classification approach and detection methodology developed by Liu and Liang (2010) [11] and further applied by Che and Zhao (2021) [12] are adopted and therefore explained in more detail. This approach is based on vertical profiles of potential temperature and is based on the principle that the structure of the ABL can be classified into three main regimes as described above: CBL, SBL, and (N)RL. Each regime has different implications for turbulence, vertical mixing, and wind profile development, and thus plays a critical role in wind farm performance and wake dynamics.

Their classification approach is based on the evaluation of the vertical gradients of the potential temperature. The key indicator is the potential temperature difference between two lower atmospheric levels, typically at 50 m (θ_2) and 250 m (θ_5) as given by Equation (14). Figure 4 shows the potential temperature profile in this

lowest part of the vertical profiles, the mixing layer, highlighting the levels between which the PTD is evaluated.

$$\text{PTD} = \theta_5 - \theta_2 \quad (14)$$

This temperature difference reflects the stratification in the lower part of the ABL and is interpreted as suggested in Equation (15). Here σ is the stability threshold, commonly set to 0.2-0.5 K in maritime environments.

$$\text{PTD} = \theta_5 - \theta_2 = \begin{cases} < -\sigma, & \text{CBL (unstable)} \\ > +\sigma, & \text{SBL (stable)} \\ \in [-\sigma, +\sigma], & \text{NRL (neutral)} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Figure 4: Representation of the simplified potential temperature profiles under different ABL conditions. The heights at which the PTD metric is evaluated, i.e., θ_2 and θ_5 , are also indicated.

The PTD method is particularly useful for this study, as it allows the identification of CBL conditions from measurements or modeled data. CBLs are of special interest due to their frequent occurrence offshore and their well-mixed thermodynamic structure, which simplifies the analysis of mesoscale flow effects on wind farm power output by reducing sensitivity to stability variations. Understanding and modeling the vertical potential temperature profile under CBL conditions is therefore crucial for fast and reliable ABL–wind farm interaction modeling. The next subsection outlines common approaches for representing this profile.

2.2.3 Modeling the Vertical Temperature Profiles of a CBL

Traditionally, a CBL is composed of four main layers: the surface layer (SL), a well-mixed layer (ML) near the ground, a stably stratified free atmosphere (FA) above, and an intermediate entrainment layer (EL), also known as the interfacial layer, that smooths the transition between the ML and the FA. Figure 5 shows the vertical profiles of key flow variables in the CBL, namely potential temperature

$\theta(z)$, wind speed $U_{\text{mag}}(z)$, and potential temperature flux $q(z)$. The different layers of the CBL are highlighted.

Figure 5: Vertical structure of the convective boundary layer (CBL), showing potential temperature $\theta(z)$, wind speed $U_{\text{mag}}(z)$, and potential temperature flux $q(z)$. Adapted from [13].

As potential temperature profiles are of particular interest in this thesis, further focus is given to this variable. Various studies in the literature have proposed simplified schemes to approximate the vertical potential temperature profile of a CBL-conditioned atmosphere. Early models primarily relied on idealized jump structures. In so-called zero-order models, a sharp discontinuity was used to represent the transition from the ML to the FA [14, 15]. Later, first-order models introduced a thin layer with constant static stability to represent the rapid thermal transition [16].

Despite the simplicity of the above models, they fall short in several ways. This becomes particularly evident when comparing their predictions to high-resolution large-eddy simulations (LES) or field measurements obtained from radiosondes, balloon soundings, and remote sensing technologies such as lidar and radar. To overcome these limitations, more recent work has introduced smooth analytical profiles that represent the CBL as a continuous transition between layers. These formulations avoid artificial discontinuities and enable more robust and physically consistent parameter fitting.

Notable efforts have been made to develop mathematical formulations that better capture gradual transitions rather than sharp jumps [17, 18]. This culminated in the work of Rampanelli and Zardi (2004), who proposed a smooth analytical function for potential temperature profile fitting. Figure 6 shows an overview of the different fitting approach with Figure 6a, Figure 6b and Figure 6c, the zero-order jump model, the first-order jump model and the smooth analytical formulation introduced by Rampanelli and Zardi [19]. For this last fitting approach, the inversion layer has a thickness denoted by Δh , with the inversion base, center and top represented by the parameters h_0 , h_1 and h_2 , respectively. The potential temperature increase across this layer, also known as the inversion strength, is given by $\Delta\theta$. The stably stratified FA above it is characterized by a lapse rate γ . θ_m is the potential temperature of the mixing layer.

Figure 6: Vertical representation of the capping inversion structure as described by: (a) zeroth-order jump models, (b) first-order jump models, and (c) the smooth analytical formulation by Rampanelli and Zardi (2004) [19]

As the Rampanelli fitting algorithm plays a central role in this thesis, where it will be used to analytically fit profiles to modeled temperature data, the following section will provide a more detailed description of the fitting approach.

2.2.4 Rampanelli Fitting Algorithm

The Rampanelli fitting algorithm provides a straightforward mathematical approach to characterize the thermal structure of the convective boundary layer through a best-fit analysis of vertical profiles. By matching a smooth, idealized temperature profile to observed or modeled data, key boundary-layer parameters—such as inversion height, inversion strength, and free-atmosphere stratification—can be consistently extracted. While the method was originally applied to radiosonde and airborne measurements, in this study it will be applied to modeled potential temperature profiles obtained from WRF and ERA5 data. Further details on the implementation are provided in later sections.

The Rampanelli temperature profile, adapted to the notation of Stipa et al., is mathematically expressed by Equation (16).

$$\theta(z) = \theta_{\text{ref}} + af(\zeta) + bg(\zeta), \quad \text{with} \quad \zeta = \frac{z-l}{c\Delta h} \quad (16)$$

In the above equation, l denotes the center of the entrainment layer, i.e., the height of the capping inversion, while Δh represents its thickness. The constant $c = \frac{1}{3}$ controls the vertical stretching of the scaled coordinate ζ . The functions $f(\zeta)$ and $g(\zeta)$, defined in Equation (17) and Equation (18), are constructed to describe the rapid transition through the inversion layer and the asymptotic increase of potential temperature in the free atmosphere, respectively (see Figure 7). Figure 7 illustrates $f(\zeta)$ (left panel) and $g(\zeta)$ (right panel). The relative weighting of

these functions is governed by the coefficients a and b , which are defined in Equation (19), where γ is the potential temperature gradient above the inversion (i.e., the free atmosphere lapse rate), and $\Delta\theta$ is the total temperature jump across the entrainment layer.

$$f(\zeta) = \frac{\tanh(\zeta) + 1}{2} \quad (17)$$

$$g(\zeta) = \frac{\ln[2 \cosh(\zeta)] + \zeta}{2} \quad (18)$$

$$b = c\gamma\Delta h, \quad a = \Delta\theta - b \quad (19)$$

Figure 7: Rampanelli basis functions: $f(\zeta)$ for the entrainment layer transition and $g(\zeta)$ for asymptotic growth in the free atmosphere.

Once the fitting is obtained, the parameters a , b , θ_m , l , and Δh can be used to identify the physical variables that characterize the structure of the atmospheric background. To connect these fitting parameters to meaningful atmospheric-layer properties, some criteria must be applied to relate the smooth analytical profile of Equation (16) to the conceptual structure. For details on the criteria and justification, reference is made to [19]. The relationships listed in Equation (23) are then used to define the free-atmosphere lapse rate γ , the inversion base and top heights h_0 and h_2 , and the reference potential temperature θ_{00} associated with a linear extrapolation of the free-atmosphere profile.

$$\gamma = \frac{2b}{\Delta h}, \quad (20)$$

$$h_0 = l - \frac{\Delta h}{2}, \quad (21)$$

$$h_2 = l + \frac{\Delta h}{2}, \quad (22)$$

$$\theta_{00} = a + \theta_m - \gamma l = a + \theta_m - \frac{2b}{\Delta h} l. \quad (23)$$

The expression for the inversion strength is not uniquely defined, as its form strongly depends on the state of the atmospheric boundary layer and the dominant growth mechanism. Therefore, we first introduce the concepts of entrainment- and encroachment-driven conditions to illustrate how $\Delta\theta$ evolves under each regime.

The evolution of the inversion strength $\Delta\theta$ at the top of the CBL is governed by the relative heating of the mixed layer and the warming of the entrainment zone through mixing with the free atmosphere. The definition adopted in this work is provided in Equation (24).

$$\Delta\theta = \theta_i - \theta_m \quad (24)$$

In this expression, θ_i denotes the potential temperature just above the inversion, within the free atmosphere, while θ_m represents the mixed-layer potential temperature. When entrainment occurs, warmer air from the free atmosphere is mixed downward, leading to an increase in θ_m . This, combined with surface heating and buoyancy-driven upward convection, causes the mixed layer to grow. Simultaneously, the inversion height h_m increases. However, since θ_i in the free atmosphere increases with height due to the background lapse rate, it may rise more rapidly than θ_m , particularly under stronger stratification. As a result, the inversion strength $\Delta\theta = \theta_i - \theta_m$ may continue to increase, even as the mixed layer becomes progressively warmer.

In contrast, under encroachment conditions, the growth of the boundary layer is driven solely by surface heating. As there is no entrainment of warmer air from the free atmosphere, the inversion strength does not increase significantly, and the capping inversion remains relatively weak. The extent to which entrainment and encroachment influence the final θ -profile is reflected in the scaling of the coefficients a and b in front of the functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ within the fitting algorithm. Figure 8 illustrates potential temperature profiles for both entrainment (left) and pure encroachment (right) conditions. A similar notation is used as in this work, except that h_m denotes the mixed-layer height and SHF represents the surface sensible heat flux [20].

Figure 8: Potential temperature profiles for the entrainment process (left) and the encroachment process (right).

Based on these insights, an expression for the inversion strength $\Delta\theta$ can be formulated to capture both entrainment and encroachment contributions. A general form is provided in Equation (25), where the inversion strength is expressed as a combination of a surface-based offset and a height-dependent term. Here, θ_0 denotes a reference potential temperature, and the scaling parameters a and b represent how both warming effectsn encroachment and entrainment, are present.

$$\Delta\theta = \theta_0 + \gamma h_2 - \theta_m = a + b \quad (25)$$

In the case of pure encroachment, entrainment is assumed negligible ($b = 0$), and therefore the dependency of $\Delta\theta$ on the free atmosphere, which is present through γ , is eliminated. However, directly using h_0 as the inversion base can result in unphysical negative values of $\Delta\theta'$, especially in limiting cases [10]. Following the approach of Deardorff (1979), the effective inversion height should instead be estimated as the midpoint between the inversion base h_0 and the upper transition height h_2 , i.e., $l = (h_0 + h_2)/2$. The resulting expression is given by Equation (26).

$$\Delta\theta' = \theta_0 + \gamma l - \theta_m = a \quad (26)$$

This formulation ensures a physically consistent representation of encroachment-dominated growth, and allows small but nonzero values of a , typically within the range $a \in [0.2, 0.5]$ K, to reflect residual contributions to the inversion strength in weakly entraining regimes.

Generally, it can be stated that the smooth nature of the Rampanelli profile avoids the ambiguity and instability often associated with piecewise or discontinuous jump models, particularly in automated fitting routines. For this reason, the Rampanelli algorithm is especially well-suited for application to model the vertical θ -profiles in this thesis, where it enables consistent estimation of boundary-layer heights and stratification characteristics.

2.3 Micro-Scale Effects in Wind Farms

This subsection is organized as follows: in Section 2.3.1, the concept of wake modeling is introduced. Next, in Section 2.3.2, a conceptual overview is given of the evolution of the most important wake models, i.e., the Jensen (Park) model, the Larsen wake model, the Dynamic Wake Meandering (DWM) model, the Fuga model, and various CFD-based models. Section 2.3.3 discusses the different wake superposition approaches.

2.3.1 Definition and Scope

Wind turbine wakes are one of the most crucial aspects of the wind energy field. Understanding the concept and modeling it as accurately as possible is essential for optimizing power forecasting, improving wind farm efficiency, and minimizing structural loads on downstream turbines. Over the past 40 years, numerous efforts have been made to develop wake models that characterize the downstream flow of wind turbines as accurately as possible, with a particular focus on two key physical phenomena.

First, there is the momentum or velocity deficit downstream of the turbine. As a consequence of this reduced available wind power, a downstream turbine experiences a decrease in power output. Secondly, since a wind turbine extracts energy from the flow at a specific location in space, the remaining energy is redistributed. Due to the strong velocity gradient between the wake flow and the surrounding free stream, increased shear stress leads to the generation of turbulent structures, resulting in higher turbulence levels. This, in turn, induces unsteady loading on downstream turbines.

In general, wake models aim to capture the physical aspects discussed above in two main regions: the near wake and the far wake. The near wake extends approximately 2 to 4 rotor diameters (D) downstream of the turbine, which is typically shorter than the distance to the next turbine, often placed around $7D$. This region is characterized by a flow that is strongly influenced by the rotor geometry, leading to the formation of blade tip vortices as well as strong velocity and pressure gradients. Additionally, this region experiences significant wake expansion. Therefore, wake modeling in this zone often takes into account detailed turbulence and vorticity dynamics to accurately represent these effects.

The far wake begins beyond the near wake, where the direct influence of rotor geometry diminishes. However, this region is still governed by turbulent mixing, which entrains ambient flow into the wake and facilitates wake recovery. The intensity and structure of this turbulence depend primarily on two sources: rotor-induced turbulence, strongly influenced by the thrust coefficient C_T and background atmospheric turbulence. In fact, C_T plays a critical role in both near and far wake development, as it governs the strength of the momentum deficit and the amount of turbulence generated by the turbine.

Wake models are generally classified on the basis of their complexity, underlying assumptions, and the physical phenomena they capture. They differ in how wake expansion and velocity deficit are represented, as well as whether turbulence and wake mixing are included. In addition, some models account for dynamic wake meandering. Lastly, atmospheric stability effects and mesoscale coupling play a crucial role in wake modeling. The latter is particularly important in this study and will be discussed in more detail later in this work.

It is trivial to say that the physics of the wind turbine wake, except for the blade tip region, can be described by the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations. However, analytical models use simplified closed-form solutions without discretization, while CFD-based models numerically solve the equations using discretization methods such as finite-volume or finite-difference approaches.

2.3.2 Existing Micro-Scale Wake Models

This section provides an overview of the evolution of wake modeling approaches, beginning with empirical and analytical models and progressing toward more advanced numerical and physics-based methods.

The Jensen Model (Jensen Park Model) and the Frandsen Model

One of the pioneering analytical wake models is the one proposed by Jensen [21]. In this model, the velocity deficit in the wake is assumed to follow a top-hat shape. This uniform velocity deficit implies the assumption of a linearly expanding wake, characterized by the wake decay coefficient k , i.e., the expansion coefficient, and is given by Equation (27) which values strongly depend on different atmospheric conditions. Equation (29) is the final expression for the normalized velocity in the wake at a specified distance x downstream of the turbine with $U_\infty(x)$ the free-stream flow, C_T the thrust coefficient, and D the diameter of the rotor. Subscripts w and r refer to wake and rotor, respectively. Making use of the 1D momentum theory, the axial induction factor a in the numerator can be rewritten in terms of the thrust coefficient C_T , according to Equation (28). For a more in detailed mathematical analysis, reference is made to literature [21].

$$D_w = D_r + 2k x \quad (27)$$

$$a = \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T}}{2} \quad (28)$$

$$\frac{U_w(x)}{U_\infty} = 1 - \frac{2a}{(1 + 2k x/D_r)^2} = 1 - \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T}}{(1 + 2k x/D_r)^2} \quad (29)$$

Although Jensen claims to have made use of the conservation of momentum to derive Equation (29), Majid Bastankhah and Fernando Porté-Agel showed that the model can be derived using only the mass conservation [22]. This was mainly due to the choice of the control volume fully downstream of the wind turbine. Later,

Frandsen et al [23] added the momentum conservation to the analysis and replaced the control volume for the analysis such that it includes one or multiple wind turbines, ending up with an expression for the normalized velocity deficit as in Equation (30). A and A_0 in the expression represent the wake area and rotor area, respectively. Note that linear wake expansion is no longer assumed since wake recovery based on turbulence is incorporated into this revised Jensen wake model.

$$\frac{U_w}{U_\infty} = \frac{1}{2} \pm \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 - 2 \frac{A_0}{A} C_T} \quad (30)$$

Both models take slightly different approaches to deriving expressions for the normalized velocity profiles in the downstream region. However, they both assume the wake region exhibits a top-hat shape and follows self-similarity, meaning that velocity profiles collapse when scaled by a characteristic length and velocity. Due to these simplifications and their computational efficiency, these models are widely used in engineering wake studies. However, their assumptions limit accuracy, making them less suitable for modeling wake behavior in complex atmospheric conditions. Additionally, they can present numerical challenges due to singular behavior near the wake edge: the sharp velocity transition between the wake and the surrounding flow leads to discontinuities in velocity gradients, which can cause instability or convergence issues in numerical solvers.

Figure 9: Schematic representation of the control volume used in analytical wake modeling. Adapted from Bastankhah and Porté-Agel [22].

From top-hat to Gaussian velocity deficit distributions

Despite the rather straightforward approach of the top-hat-shaped wake models for estimating velocity deficits in wind farms, concerns arose regarding their accuracy. Katic et al. [24] claimed that these models fail to accurately describe wake velocity and instead only provide an estimate of the available energy. Since available wind power varies with the cube of the wind speed, incorrectly estimating wind speed can result in significant errors in power predictions.

Extensive research on the wakes behind bluff bodies in free flows has shown that a self-similar Gaussian profile emerges in the far-wake region [25, 26, 27].

Building on this, Bastankhah & Porté-Agel (2014) introduced a wake model that uses an axisymmetric Gaussian distribution to describe the velocity deficit instead of the traditional top-hat assumption, while ensuring self-similarity. Note that the presence of a Gaussian velocity deficit in turbine far wakes has been confirmed through wind tunnel experiments (e.g., [28]) and numerical simulations (e.g., [29]).

This wake model is based on both mass and momentum conservation, and the Gaussian velocity deficit is given by Equation (31) with the maximum velocity deficit in the center of the wake being estimated by Equation (32), and the wake width σ by Equation (33). In the last expression, k denotes the wake expansion parameter as defined earlier, and $\varepsilon = 0.2\beta$, with β being a function of the turbine thrust coefficient C_T .

$$\frac{\Delta U}{U_\infty} = C(x)e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (31)$$

$$C(x) = 1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{C_T}{8(\sigma/d_0)^2}} \quad (32)$$

$$\frac{\sigma}{d_0} = k\frac{x}{d_0} + \varepsilon \quad (33)$$

Substituting Equation (32) and Equation (33) into Equation (31) and normalizing the expression gives Equation (34), in which x represents the downstream distance, z_H the turbine hub height, and y and z the spanwise and vertical coordinates, respectively. Bastankhah and Porté-Agel compared their model with high-resolution wind tunnel measurements and LES data, concluding that this model provides better results in both full-wake and partial-wake conditions compared to older top-hat wake models [22]. Consequently, it yields a more realistic velocity distribution than previously assumed models. As a result, the Bastankhah–Porté-Agel model is widely used in engineering applications and is also implemented in wake modeling frameworks such as PyWake, which is employed in this work.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta U}{U_\infty} = & \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{C_T}{8(k^*x/d_0 + \varepsilon)^2}} \right) \\ & \times \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2(k^*x/d_0 + \varepsilon)^2} \left\{ \left(\frac{z - z_h}{d_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{y}{d_0} \right)^2 \right\} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Incorporating turbulence intensity effects to model the local wake growth

Introducing the Gaussian wake model provided significant improvements in power forecasting models over the traditional top-hat models. However, the above models do not account for the influence of turbulence intensity (TI) on the wake growth and therefore lack accuracy given a certain atmospheric inflow condition. Niayifar and Porté-Agel further built upon those models by incorporating turbulence intensity and its effects on the local wake growth rate [30]. In their formulation, the wake growth rate parameter k is no longer a condition fixed on the basis of

experimental data, but is dynamically related to TI , allowing the model to capture the variability in wake recovery under different atmospheric conditions. The wake width $\sigma(x)$ is given by Equation (35), in which the wake expansion coefficient k is now expressed as Section 7.4. The constants a_s and b_s are empirically determined from LES simulations. This expression ensures that the wake expands faster under highly turbulent conditions and therefore also recovers more quickly.

$$\sigma(x) = k(TI)x + \sigma_0 \quad (35)$$

$$k(TI) = a_s TI + b_s \quad (36)$$

Later, C. Fuertes et al. (2018) validated the above analytical model using data from lidars mounted on the nacelle of a wind turbine, scanning both upstream and downstream [31]. Their research demonstrated that, after updating the empirical parameters with the available data, the existing models accurately predict wake expansion, velocity deficit, and the length of the near-wake region.

Numerically Supported Analytical Wake Model

The research by Niayifar and Porte-Agel [30] was based on conditions in which the wind turbines operated within a range of wind speeds in which the thrust coefficient C_T remained approximately constant. Consequently, the wake growth rate is primarily assumed to be a function of the local streamwise turbulence intensity I_a . However, since the thrust coefficient (C_T) varies under different atmospheric conditions, T. Ishihara and G. Qian (2018) [32] incorporated both ambient turbulence intensity and thrust coefficient effects into the wake expansion dynamics to enhance model accuracy under variable stability conditions. Using Large Eddy Simulation (LES) data and wind tunnel experiments, they developed an improved wake model that explicitly accounts for the influence of ambient turbulence intensity (I_a) and thrust coefficient (C_T). Equation (37) shows the new expression for the wake width as a function of both parameters. Including C_T into the definition ensures a slower wake recovery for higher values, while increased I_a values results in faster mixing and wake dissipation.

$$\sigma(x) = (0.11C_T^{1.07}I_a^{0.20})x + (0.23C_T^{-0.25}I_a^{0.17}) \quad (37)$$

Similar to the wake models of Bastankhah and Porté-Agel (2014) [22] and Niayifar and Porté-Agel (2016) [30], T. Ishihara and G. Qian (2018) [32] retained the Gaussian profile for velocity deficit but introduced modifications to account for thrust-dependent wake dynamics, i.e., a correction term is implemented to account for this. This new formulation is given by Equation (38) with an expression for wake model parameters a , b and p provided in the Table 2. The p -factor in this expression acts as the before mentioned correction factor to improve the model's accuracy for short distances behind the rotor. This analytical formulation was supported by numerical simulations, conducted to investigate the effects of thrust-dependent wake behavior and validate the modified wake model against reference datasets. Additionally, these simulations provided insights into the sensitivity of the model parameters.

$$\frac{\Delta U}{U_\infty} = \frac{1}{\left(a + b\frac{x}{D} + p\right)^2} \exp\left(-\frac{r^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (38)$$

Table 2: Wake Model Parameters for Zong Wake Model

Parameter	Expression
a	$0.93 C_T^{-0.75} I_a^{0.17}$
b	$0.42 C_T^{0.6} I_a^{0.2}$
p	$0.15 C_T^{-0.25} I_a^{-0.7} (1 + x/D)^{-2}$

The super-Gaussian wind turbine wake model

All the above analytical models share a common limitation: they are primarily designed to estimate far-wake characteristics, typically valid at downstream distances greater than four rotor diameters (d_0). As modern wind farms increasingly adopt denser layouts, the importance of accurately modeling near-wake dynamics has grown. The Lillgrund wind farm for instance has a turbine spacing of 3.3 wind turbine diameters, requiring analytical models that can accurately predict the near wake [33]. Consequently, recent efforts have focused on extending or reformulating these far-wake models to better capture the flow behavior in the near-wake region.

Due to the choice of the Gaussian shape for the velocity deficit and the application of mass and momentum conservation in a control volume around the wind turbine, the maximum velocity deficit is assumed to decrease with increasing downstream distance. However, numerical and experimental studies have shown that the Gaussian shape assumption does not hold as suggested by the aforementioned wake models but rather evolves from a top-hat shape in the near wake to a Gaussian shape in the far wake [34]. This can be explained by the presence of tip vortices, which originate at the blade tips and induce wake mixing as they break up further downstream, causing the wake velocity deficit to gradually develop into a Gaussian-shaped structure [33].

This issue has been neglected in the analytical wake models discussed above, with the exception of the wake model proposed by Qian and Ishihara (2018) [32], which introduced a correction factor p to improve near-wake velocity deficit estimations. However, the inclusion of this correction factor results in a violation of mass and momentum conservation. Nevertheless, it is crucial to have a proper formulation of the velocity deficit throughout the entire downstream wake to ensure that the analytical model is applicable to wind farms of all sizes, including those with both large and small inter-turbine spacing.

Blondel & Cathelain (2020) [33] developed a new analytical wake model introducing a super-Gaussian shape function for the evolution of the velocity deficit

downstream, transitioning from a near top-hat shape, similar to the Jensen model, in the near wake to a Gaussian-shaped velocity deficit in the far wake. The general equation for the velocity deficit in this super-Gaussian wake model is given by Equation (39). It is worth noting that this expression is similar to the one provided by Bastankhah, i.e., Equation (31), but with an additional Gaussian order n , which varies depending on the wake evolution. High values of n represent the near wake, while low values of n correspond to the far wake. The maximum velocity deficit function $C(x)$ is determined by Equation (40). Notably, when $n = 2$, the velocity deficit profile is purely Gaussian, and Equation (40) reduces to the original form of $C(x)$ as proposed by Bastankhah and Porté-Agel [22, 33].

$$\frac{\Delta U}{U_\infty} = C(x)e^{-\bar{r}^n/(2\sigma^2)} \quad (39)$$

$$C(x) = 2^{2/n-1} - \sqrt{2^{4/n-2} - \frac{nC_T}{16\Gamma(2/n)\sigma^{4/n}}} \quad (40)$$

Physics-Based Models

The wake models discussed so far were all analytical in nature, i.e., Jensen [21], Frandsen [35], Bastankhah and Porté-Agel [22], and Niayifar and Porté-Agel [30], with the exception of the hybrid approach introduced by T. Ishihara and G. Qian (2018) [32], which incorporates empirical adjustments to improve wake predictions. Although these analytical models provide fast and practical implementations for engineering applications, they are strongly simplified, relying on assumptions that do not fully capture the interaction between wake dynamics and atmospheric stability effects. To address this limitation, physics-based models are introduced.

It is trivial to state that the wake dynamics problem, like other fluid dynamic problems, is governed mathematically by the Navier-Stokes equations. Equation (41) and Equation (42) below represent the continuity equation (conservation of mass) and the momentum equation (conservation of momentum), formulated using the Einstein notation and expressed in Cartesian coordinates [35]. Note that, in practice, the Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations are typically used.

$$\frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_j} = 0 \quad (41)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + u_j \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (2\nu S_{ij}) + f_i \quad (42)$$

Here u_i represents the velocity components, while x_j denotes the position vector components. P is the pressure, ρ is the fluid density, ν is the kinematic viscosity, and f_i represents external body forces. The variable t refers to time, and the subscripts i and j indicate the directional components. The strain rate tensor S_{ij} is defined in Equation (43).

$$S_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right). \quad (43)$$

A further distinction is made between RANS-based models and LES-based models, with the main difference being how turbulence is modeled. In RANS-based models, the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations are used together with turbulence closure models, which introduce additional equations to express the Reynolds stress terms of known or computable variables. This approach allows for the inclusion of atmospheric stability effects and wake interactions, providing a more realistic representation of wake dynamics while maintaining relatively low computational costs. In contrast, LES-based models (Large Eddy Simulations) resolve turbulence down to smaller scales, capturing detailed wake dynamics, including shear effects and atmospheric stability influences. While LES-based models yield highly accurate results, they are computationally expensive as they aim to resolve turbulence down to the inertial range of turbulence. Therefore LES models are primary for research and high-fidelity studies rather than for routine engineering applications.

An example of a RANS-based wake model is the Fuga model, developed by DTU Wind Energy, which aims to predict wake effects in offshore wind farms [36]. This linearized CFD model applies eddy viscosity theory to address the turbulence closure problem, i.e., an eddy viscosity coefficient is used to relate the Reynolds stress terms to the mean strain rate. In a later update of the model, atmospheric stability effects were incorporated by adjusting the eddy viscosity profile according to atmospheric conditions, thereby enhancing wake recovery predictions. This adjustment is achieved by relating the eddy viscosity K to the wind speed gradient of the velocity profile, as given by Equation (44).

$$K(z) = \frac{u_*^2}{dU/dz} \quad (44)$$

The model has been validated using production data from the Horns Rev 1 offshore wind farm, showing good agreement under neutral and unstable conditions, while performance under strongly stable conditions remains challenging due to numerical solver limitations. Compared to LES-based models, Fuga provides a computationally efficient approach for engineering applications by modeling single-wake dynamics through linearized steady-state RANS. While it captures key perturbations around a mean flow, its applicability is limited to moderate thrust coefficients ($C_T 0.6$) due to the underlying linear assumptions. Additionally, wake interactions in wind farms are treated via a superposition model, making Fuga an alternative to empirical wake models, such as Gaussian or top-hat formulations, rather than a substitute for high-fidelity LES [36].

2.3.3 Wake Superposition Methods

The wake models previously discussed mainly focus on the wake dynamics of individual wind turbines. However, in actual wind farms, wakes from multiple turbines interact, leading to cumulative wake effects that influence the performance of downstream turbines. Although some studies have employed LES to investi-

gate wake interactions in smaller wind farms for parameter validation [32], these high-fidelity methods are often computationally expensive. To efficiently estimate the overall wake deficit in larger wind farms, various wake superposition models have been proposed. These models aim to approximate the combined velocity deficit by superimposing the effects of individual wakes, using various mathematical approaches. The four most commonly used methods are briefly introduced here: Geometric Sum, Linear Sum, Energy Balance and Quadratic Sum. Table 3 lists these wake superposition models with their corresponding mathematical expression [37].

The Geometric Sum Model evaluates the velocity at a downstream turbine based on the product of velocity ratios of upstream turbines in the flow direction. U_∞ is the free-stream wind speed, u_{n+1} represents the wind speed at the downstream wind turbine where the velocity deficit is evaluated and u_j is the wind speed at each upstream wind turbine j affecting the downstream turbine. The total number of upstream wind turbines is n .

While the Geometric Sum Model assumes a multiplicative wake interaction, the Linear Sum Model has a rather simple approach and assumes that each upstream wind turbine independently contributes to the total velocity deficit. So the formulas given by Table 3 represent a summation of individual wake losses.

Although the Linear Sum Model is computational efficient because of its rather simple approach, it does not fulfill the conservation of energy law. This can result in big inaccuracies in wake prediction. To address this, the Energy Balance Model is introduced, which is based on conservation of the kinetic energy when summing the wake effects. It states that the sum of kinetic energy losses to momentum extraction by the turbine should be consistent with the turbulent mixing process downstream.

However, wake interaction under different atmospheric conditions follows a non-linear nature, i.e., wake effects of different turbines can not be simply added up in a straightforward linear manner since they interact and modify each other in reality. To account for this, the Quadratic Sum Model is introduced. This model is of particular interest for offshore wind farms, where the wakes persist longer.

Wake Superposition Model	Formula
Geometric Sum	$\frac{u_{n+1}}{U_\infty} = \prod_{j=1}^n \frac{u_{j+1}}{u_j}$
Linear Sum	$\left(1 - \frac{u_{n+1}}{U_\infty}\right) = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{u_{j+1}}{u_j}\right)$
Energy Balance	$(U_\infty^2 - u_{n+1}^2) = \sum_{j=1}^n (u_j^2 - u_{j+1}^2)$
Quadratic Sum	$\left(1 - \frac{u_{n+1}}{U_\infty}\right)^2 = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{u_{j+1}}{u_j}\right)^2$

Table 3: Expressions for most used Wake Superposition Models, according to [35]

Habenicht did a comparison between the different models for various offshore wind farms and concluded that both the Linear Sum Model and the Quadratic Sum Model show results that agree best with measurement data [38].

2.4 Meso-Scale Effects Induced by Wind Farms

While micro-scale effects such as turbine wakes and local turbulence dominate the flow near individual wind turbines, the cumulative influence of an entire wind farm can give rise to larger-scale flow phenomena that extend well beyond the farm boundaries. These meso-scale effects emerge from the interaction between the ABL and the momentum and buoyancy deficits induced by the turbines. The primary meso-scale phenomena include global wind farm blockage, farm-induced pressure gradients, and the excitation of gravity waves under stratified atmospheric conditions. Section 2.4.1 and Section 2.4.2 provide a detailed explanation of these effects, followed by a discussion of their impact on the surrounding flow in Section 2.4.3. Finally, the importance of accounting for these meso-scale effects into flow modeling is discussed in Section 2.4.4.

2.4.1 Global Wind Farm Blockage and Pressure Effects

The previous section discussed how aerodynamic wake effects from upstream turbines influence the power production of downstream turbines, with dependencies on factors such as turbine spacing and layout. However, a significant additional phenomenon has recently gained attention: even the power output of the first row of turbines often deviates from the free-stream wind field measured far upstream or before farm construction. [39]

Bleeg et al. [40] investigated three wind farm configurations for which meteorological masts were installed prior to their construction and commercial operation. Their analysis revealed that the presence of the wind farm reduces the upstream wind speed. This phenomenon is known as the global blockage effect. Additionally to this, RANS simulations further supported these observations, showing that neglecting the global blockage effect can lead to an overestimation of the predicted AEP by up to 5%. Similarly, Sebastiani et al. [41] collected wind field measurements both before and after the construction of the Lillgrund wind farm, using these data as input for wake model simulations. Their analysis revealed an overestimate of nearly 4% in predicted power production, attributed to farm-induced upstream deceleration effects. Later, Schneemann et al. [42] successfully observed this meso-scale effect using LiDAR measurements and emphasized that its appearance is strongly influenced by the stability conditions of the ABL.

Bleeg et al. [40] pointed out that the assumption of the classical wakes-only approach as being valid is incorrect, since it primarily focuses on turbine interactions occurring downstream of the rotor. In attempts to address modeling this upstream deceleration, local-blockage effects were introduced, such as the empirical formulation of Troldborg and Meyer Forsting (2017), the Rankine half-body model of

Gribben and Hawkes, the vortex cylinder model, and the linearized model by Segalini (2021). These models assess the global blockage effect by a simple linear superposition of the local blockage effects. When comparing these models with numerical simulations, they seem to perform well.

However, when thermal stratification is present, the linear superposition of individual turbine effects is no longer valid and leads to a significant underestimation of power output [43]. Although individual turbine blockage is still well captured, even under stratified conditions, comparisons with LES reveal that a key limitation of engineering models is their inability to represent wind farm–ABL interactions accurately. This deficiency becomes more pronounced as wind farm size increases and ABL height decreases. These findings suggest that under farm–ABL interacting conditions, the individual turbine induction models highly underestimate the share of each individual turbine induction in the the global blockage effect [43]. A visualization of this effect is provided in Figure 10, which displays iso-surfaces of a 1% velocity deficit for both a single turbine (in red) and the entire wind farm (in gray). The red surface illustrates the local induction effect commonly captured by traditional models. The gray surface highlights how cumulative, farm-scale interactions with the atmosphere can lead to a much broader upstream velocity deficit, often referred to as global blockage, where a simple superposition of individual turbine effects falls short in capturing the full extent of the phenomenon.

Figure 10: Illustration of the global blockage effect under wind farm–ABL interaction. A simple superposition of local turbine induction effects underestimates the cumulative farm-scale induction. Adapted from Flaszynski et al. [39].

In addition to the direct impact of cumulative turbine induction, recent studies have shown that additional mechanisms contribute to this upstream flow deceleration, particularly under stratified atmospheric conditions [42]. Allaerts and Meyers [44] studied the ABL development and gravity waves in conventionally neutral wind farms. There, he states that although gravity waves, see Section 2.4.2, only exist in the inversion layer and the free atmosphere, the associated pressure perturbations are imposed on the boundary layer and modify the wind farm flow, being

directly related to the observed upstream flow deceleration. Wu and Porté-Agel [45] attributed the upstream flow deceleration to the combined effect of both cumulative turbine induction and the triggering of gravity waves by the adverse pressure gradient in front of the wind farm. Additionally, they suggest that the balance between these mechanisms is highly dependent on the atmospheric stability. In order to understand this, the concept of gravity waves is first briefly introduced.

2.4.2 The generation of Gravity Waves by Wind Farm

The previous section highlighted the effect of stability on the likelihood of existence and strength of gravity waves, with a stable atmosphere being most prone to trigger them. Their formation can be understood using the concept introduced in Section 2.1.2, which explained how a displaced air parcel in a stable atmosphere experiences a restoring buoyancy force, leading to oscillatory vertical motion. Additionally, [46] describes how, in classical mountain wave theory, vertically propagating gravity waves are triggered by the presence of orographic obstacles in a stratified flow. An analogy can be made in wind farm physics, where large wind farms act as extended localized momentum sinks, comparable to a wall in the atmospheric flow [44]. The accumulated deceleration caused by the wind farm perturbs the stratified flow, creating a pressure gradient, with higher pressure upstream and lower pressure downstream. Unlike in an unstable atmosphere, the pressure disturbance cannot be balanced out horizontally under stable conditions, and consequently, the air is pushed upward. The displaced air then oscillates around its equilibrium position, resulting in the formation of gravity waves.

As mentioned in the previous paragraph, the likelihood of triggering gravity waves is related to the atmospheric stability, more specifically, the stability of the inversion layer and the free atmosphere aloft. As discussed in the work of Smith [47], the behavior of gravity waves depends on the Froude number (Fr), which compares the flow speed to the internal wave speed in a stratified atmosphere. The Froude number is defined by Equation (45), where U_b is the bulk velocity within the ABL, H is the inversion height or ABL-height, and g' is the reduced gravity defined in Equation (46). In the latter expression, $\Delta\theta$ represents the inversion strength, and θ_0 is the reference potential temperature.

$$Fr = \frac{U_b}{\sqrt{g' \cdot H}} \quad (45)$$

$$g' = \frac{g \cdot \Delta\theta}{\theta_0} \quad (46)$$

Under subcritical conditions ($Fr < 1$), interfacial gravity waves can propagate upstream, as their group velocity exceeds the advection speed of the flow. This upstream propagation leads to pressure disturbances that modify the ABL structure ahead of the wind farm, contributing to a stronger blockage effect. These interactions are particularly pronounced under stable stratification, which supports wave formation and propagation. In contrast, under supercritical conditions ($Fr > 1$), gravity waves are largely confined to the downstream region, and the waves lose

their ability to propagate upstream.

In addition to the interfacial waves described above, internal gravity waves can also arise. However, their formation mechanism differs, and the corresponding Froude number formulation is therefore slightly different, as it depends on the stability within the ABL rather than at the ABL-free atmosphere interface. Although they are not the focus of this work, they are briefly noted here for completeness. These waves form within the ABL itself, particularly under weak to moderate stratification, and are driven by buoyancy-induced vertical oscillations of air parcels. Unlike interfacial waves, which occur at the ABL-free atmosphere (FA) boundary, internal waves propagate within the boundary layer and may influence flow dynamics, especially when interfacial wave propagation is limited, such as under supercritical flow conditions. [48].

Therefore, the generation and strength of wind farm-induced gravity waves are closely linked to flow speed, ABL height, inversion strength, and the overall stratification profile. Both interfacial and internal waves contribute to these dynamics, with their relative importance depending on the flow regime and stability structure. Figure 11 presents a visualization of interfacial gravity waves generated both upstream and downstream of a wind farm, based on LES results under CNBL conditions, conducted by Lanzilao et al. [49].

Figure 11: Illustration of the formation of gravity waves around a wind farm. Adapted from Lanzilao et al. [49].

2.4.3 Flow Adaptation and Recovery at the Meso-Scale

The pressure field induced by interfacial gravity waves plays a key role in redistributing energy throughout a wind farm, and its presence is strongly linked to atmospheric stability. Therefore, atmospheric stability highly influences how the flow adapts around and over a wind farm. Allaerts and Meyers [44] showed that under stable conditions, the global blockage effect reduces streamwise mass transport. To conserve mass, the flow compensates by slightly accelerating below

the inversion layer and lifting the inversion through flow divergence and streamline displacement. This behavior is illustrated in Figure 12, which shows a snapshot from the study by Allaerts and Meyers [44].

Figure 12: Illustration of the lifting of the inversion layer—both the base and the top—under stable atmospheric conditions. Adapted from Allaerts and Meyers [44].

Building upon these insights, Strickland et al. (2022) [50] showed that the deflection of relatively cold, high-density air over the wind farm in stable conditions creates a localized high-pressure region at the farm entrance. The resulting pressure build-up amplifies the adverse pressure gradient upstream, thereby increasing flow deceleration and strengthening the global blockage effect.

Conversely, in unstable atmospheric conditions, where strong surface heating induces convective turbulence and enhanced vertical mixing, the airflow is more prone to horizontal deflection around the wind farm. The increased background turbulence allows the flow to adjust laterally, acting as a horizontal spreader of the reduced-velocity zones and thereby weakening the strength of the global blockage effect. As a consequence, this reduces the need for vertical displacement over the turbines. Schneemann et al. (2021) [42] observed that in unstable boundary layers, the global blockage effect is largely diminished due to strong vertical mixing, therefore minimizing upstream flow deceleration.

2.4.4 The Importance of Accounting for meso-scale effects in Flow Modeling

The aforementioned studies clearly show that global blockage effects can no longer be neglected, as they cause a measurable reduction in upstream wind speeds, leading to overestimations of AEP by up to 5% compared to RANS-simulations [40]. The magnitude of this blockage effect is highly dependent from the stability of the atmosphere and can be even larger for densely packed wind farms with smaller turbine spacing [39]. Field campaigns like the GLOBE project have validated and justified the global blockage theory, further emphasizing the need to capture meso-scale processes such as pressure adjustments, gravity wave generation, and flow adaptation [51].

Accurate prediction of wind farm power output requires accounting not only for micro-scale wake effects but also for meso-scale atmospheric responses induced

by the farm itself. While high-fidelity LES are capable of resolving the full spectrum of micro- and meso-scale interactions, their substantial computational cost makes them limited in their use for routine wind farm design and optimization [45, 50]. To address this limitation, recent studies have proposed enhanced engineering models that incorporate key mesoscale effects. The following section provides an overview of existing engineering models that link microscale and mesoscale flow effects, commonly referred to as coupling models.

2.5 Coupled Micro–Meso Scale Modeling

This section highlights the importance and necessity of coupling models across multiple atmospheric scales and provides an overview of existing coupling strategies. Particular attention is given to the Multi-Scale Coupled (MSC) model developed by Stipa (2024), as it closely aligns with the modeling approach employed in the DTU in-house code. Since the DTU model has not yet been officially published, this section also briefly discusses the key adaptations made in comparison to the MSC model.

2.5.1 The Need for Coupling in Wind Farm Modeling

The previous discussion highlights the importance of accurately modeling both micro-scale wake interactions and meso-scale atmospheric dynamics to predict wind farm power output under realistic conditions. Micro-scale effects, such as wake-induced flow deceleration and redirection, can propagate and significantly influence meso-scale structures, especially under stable atmospheric conditions where vertical mixing is limited. This necessitates a coupled micro-meso scale modeling approach that balances physical realism with computational cost.

LES simulations have been useful in identifying the mechanisms behind farm-atmosphere interactions. For instance, Sanchez-Gomez et al. (2023) demonstrated that vertical advection of horizontal momentum plays a key role in driving the global blockage effect — an influence that is not captured by traditional engineering models relying on the superposition of individual turbine induction zones [37]. However, while LES provides detailed insights, its high computational cost renders it impractical for routine use in wind farm design or real-time forecasting.

To address this, researchers have developed faster, engineering-models that takes into account these key physical insights from LES without having the computational cost that goes with it. In the next paragraph an overview will be given about the different engineering models that attempt to model this complex multi-scale interaction effects.

2.5.2 Existing Coupled Modeling Approaches

The idea of coupling different scales was first introduced by Frandsen et al. [23], who highlighted already in 2006 that as wind farms grow in size, there would be

a need for models capable of handling both single turbines and multi-turbine configurations within a continuously changing ABL. Linking small- and large-scale features in this context is essential. Later, Stevens et al. [52] introduced the Coupled Wake Boundary Layer (CWBL) model, which combines the top-down model of Calaf et al. [53] with existing wake models to improve power predictions. This top-down model conceptualizes large wind farms as a roughness element within the ABL, modifying the vertical wind profile due to turbine-induced momentum sinks. When coupling this with a wake model, the estimated power output is adjusted to reflect the impact of the wind farm on the ABL. A conceptual sketch of this CWBL can be seen on Figure 13.

Figure 13: Conceptual sketch illustrating the interaction between the wake model and the top-down atmospheric model. Adapted from Stevens et al. [52].

An important limitation of the original CWBL model is that it assumes a fully developed internal boundary layer (IBL) starting at the entrance of the wind farm. However, this assumption does not always hold, especially in the entrance region or in spatially non-uniform layouts. To address this, the Area-Localized Coupled (ALC) model was later introduced, in which the top-down model parameters are no longer uniform across the wind farm but instead vary locally based on turbine density and wake overlap in different regions.

The limitation of all the above-mentioned models is that they do not account for the thermal stratification of ABL, and therefore disregard the amplification effects that scale coupling can have on the global blockage effect under certain stability regimes. To address this, the Three-Layer Model (3LM) was proposed by Al-laerts and Meyers [48], which explicitly aimed to capture the multi-scale coupling between wind farms and the stratified atmosphere. This model is an enhanced version of the earlier Two-Layer Model (2LM) developed by Smith [47], which divided the atmosphere into two distinct layers: the turbine-affected ABL and the free atmosphere aloft. As mentioned in section 2.4, Smith’s model successfully demonstrated that the momentum sink created by the turbines arises from a combined influence of microscale flow effects and mesoscale pressure adjustments.

Building on this, the 3LM introduced a middle interfacial layer representing the inversion zone between the ABL and the free atmosphere, as shown in Figure 14. This model successfully captures the dynamics of internal and interfacial gravity waves, as well as the influence of atmospheric stratification and upstream pressure buildup, resulting in a free-stream wind speed correction that can be used in conventional wake models. The 3LM suffers from two limitations. Firstly, the model solves for depth-averaged velocities, meaning that there is an average wind speed for each of the three layers. This complicates the coupling with wake models since those are often designed with height-specific wind speed values, i.e., different wind speed values over the height range of the rotor area, rather than a layer-averaged wind speed. The latter approach lacks vertical detail, as wind shear and turbulent mixing variation are disregarded, which is important to have for load calculation, etc. . Additionally, the 3LM coupling method only transfers the gross wind farm blockage. This means that the model does not resolve or transfer the effect of those gravity waves into the turbine-scale flow field, i.e., within the wind farm and in the wake region downstream.

Figure 14: Conceptual sketch of the three-layer model (3LM) describing wind-farm–ABL interactions. Adapted from Allaerts and Meyers [48].

To bridge this gap, the Multi-Scale Coupled (MSC) model was introduced by Stipa et al. (2024), providing a framework that couples the 3LM with any of the wake models discussed in Section 2.3.1. This approach enables the simultaneous prediction of micro-scale effects at the turbine scale—such as individual wake interactions and rotor induction—and meso-scale phenomena at the wind farm scale and beyond, including atmospheric gravity waves. This is done through an iterative procedure. Since the MSC model acts as a basis for the in house multi-scale coupling model, the next subsection delves a bit deeper into the used submodel and the modeling approach that are used.

2.5.3 The Multi-Scale Coupled Model

As mentioned above, the MSC model by Stipa (2024) is the most recent published coupling model and forms the basis for the coupling framework used in this the-

sis, with some adaptations that will be clarified later. This multi-scale coupling approach allows for the simultaneous prediction of microscale effects at the turbine level and mesoscale phenomena at the wind farm scale. By combining different submodels and developing appropriate coupling techniques, the method establishes interdependence between the different scales. This is achieved through an iterative procedure that enables communication between both models until convergence is reached. The aimed result is the most accurate possible turbine power prediction while taking all-scale atmospheric effects into account. Figure 15 below is a snapshot of Stipa's paper about the MSC framework, in which the solution procedure of it is presented in a flowchart with the color of the boxes presenting the scale at which the process happens. Blue and green represent operations at the meso-scale and micro-scale levels, respectively.

Figure 15: Flowchart illustrating the solution procedure of the MSC model. The color coding indicates the scale of each process, with green boxes corresponding to microscale operations and blue boxes representing mesoscale processes. Adapted from Stipa et al. [5].

The first step sets up the background atmospheric state, serving as a foundation of the entire modeling process. Changing those will have a significant effect on the resulting output. The background conditions can be considered to be undisturbed, i.e., they represent the state of the atmosphere in the absence of the wind farm. Table 11 list up the different variables that are initialized.

Variable	Explanation
$U(z)$	Streamwise wind speed as a function of height
$V(z)$	Spanwise wind speed as a function of height
$\tau_{xz}(z)$	Shear stress in the xz plane
$\tau_{yz}(z)$	Shear stress in the yz plane
$\nu_t(z)$	Eddy viscosity profile (models turbulent momentum diffusion)
$\Phi(z)$	Background wind angle profile [°]
$\Delta\theta$	Potential temperature difference across the inversion layer
θ_0	Reference potential temperature
γ	Lapse rate in the free atmosphere
φ	Latitude [°]
z_0	Surface roughness length
u^*	Background friction velocity (linked to shear stress at layer interfaces)
TI_∞	Free-stream (ambient) turbulence intensity
<i>turbines</i>	Turbine layout and parameters (positions, rotor diameter, etc.)

Table 4: Input variables for the initialization of the background state in the MSC model.

The background state initialized in this step is then used to compute the thrust force exerted by each turbine on the flow by running the microscale wake models. At this stage, a choice can be made between using a wake model that accounts for local induction effects or one that does not. Since a uniform inflow is assumed, all turbines are initially subjected to the same free-stream wind speed. During this process, the initial thrust force and C_T are calculated for each turbine. Next, the coupling loop is entered and the initialized thrust is used as an input to the 3LM, the meso-scale flow solver. This model aims to solve the linearized, height-dependent momentum equations under the assumption of small perturbations $\mathbf{u} = (u, v)$ around a uniform background flow (U, H) in the first two layers, and takes the form given by Equation (47), adapted from unpublished work by Alexander M. Forsting [54].

$$UV \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial x} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla_{HP} + f_c \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{u} + \frac{\mathbf{C}^+ \Delta \mathbf{u}^+ - \mathbf{C}^- \Delta \mathbf{u}^-}{H} + \nu_t \nabla_H^2 \mathbf{u} + \frac{\mathbf{f}}{H} \quad (47)$$

The left-hand side (LHS) of the equation represents the advection of the perturbation velocity. This term describes the downstream transport of small perturbations in the velocity field by the background flow. The first term on the right-hand side (RHS) represents the horizontal pressure gradient force, i.e. ∇_{hP} , which drives acceleration and deceleration in the flow. This term is particularly important when modeling gravity waves and the pressure gradients they generate. The second term on the RHS is the Coriolis term, which represents the deflection of air due to Earth's rotation. The Coriolis parameter f_c is defined as $f_c = 2\Omega \sin \phi$, where Ω is Earth's rotation rate and ϕ is the latitude. The expression $\mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{u}$ denotes the cross-product operator, capturing the rotational deflection of the flow in the Northern Hemisphere. Next, the interlayer shear stress term accounts for vertical mixing between the different layers considered in the model, with $\Delta \mathbf{u}^\pm$ denoting the velocity jump between adjacent horizontal layers and \mathbf{C}^\pm representing the friction

at the layer interfaces. The fourth term is the horizontal turbulent diffusion term, which describes the spreading of momentum in the horizontal direction due to turbulence. The parameter ν_t represents the horizontal eddy viscosity, also known as the turbulent diffusion coefficient. The operator $\nabla_H^2 \mathbf{u}$ denotes the horizontal Laplacian of the velocity field. The final term represents the wind farm thrust force, which is computed from the wake model in the previous step of the scheme. It represents the momentum extracted by turbine thrust, distributed across the control volume (as indicated by the division by the ABL height H). For more details about the formulations of the different terms as well as a complete overview of the obtained NS-formulations, reference is made to literature [5].

The next step involves the reconstruction of the background flow, referred to as the 3LMR. In this stage, the perturbation pressure field obtained from the original 3LM is used to compute the corresponding perturbation velocity field. However, these depth-averaged perturbed quantities cannot yet be used as input for the micro-scale wake models, and therefore a background velocity reconstruction step is introduced. Here, the transformation into an actual height-dependent velocity profile is performed at each turbine location. For this study, a new method was developed that matches the local background velocity profile with the layer-averaged velocity within the wind farm. A conceptual illustration of this process is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Conceptual sketch of background velocity reconstruction using the pressure perturbation derived from the mesoscale model. Adapted from Stipa et al. [5].

Using the updated velocity profiles, the thrust coefficient is recalculated for each turbine, thereby updating the forcing term \mathbf{f} in Equation (47), which was initialized earlier. With this updated forcing, the coupling loop restarts: the meso-scale model is re-solved using the new input, a revised pressure field is obtained, and

the background velocity field is reconstructed. This updated velocity field then feeds back into the micro-scale model, completing the loop. This iterative exchange between the micro- and meso-scale models continues until convergence is reached, i.e., when successive updates to the flow and forcing terms become negligibly small.

Convergence is evaluated based on the relative change in perturbation pressure, using the L^2 -norm between two consecutive iterations. The iterative loop ends once this residual falls below a tolerance, typically $\varepsilon < 10^{-4}$, ensuring consistency between background flow and turbine forcing.

3 Study Area and Data Description

The region of interest for this study is the German Bight, located in the southeastern North Sea and bordered by Germany, Denmark, and the Netherlands. The analysis focuses on the Amrumbank West wind farm, part of the N4 cluster consisting of three adjacent offshore wind farms: Amrumbank West, Nordsee Ost, and Meerwind Süd/Ost. The OWA GLOBE campaign [51] (Global Blockage Effect) targeted the two northernmost farms, Amrumbank West and Nordsee Ost, to investigate large-scale wake interactions and global blockage effects in densely developed offshore regions. Meerwind Süd/Ost did not participate in the GLOBE campaign, which means its SCADA data is not available for this study. Figure 17 presents a geographical map of the German Bight, with the *N4 cluster* highlighted by a white frame.

Figure 17: Overview of the German Bight region. The white frame encompasses the N4 Cluster

To provide experimental validation for this thesis, the case study makes use of a comprehensive set of observational data, including SCADA records, lidar measurements, and meteorological mast observations obtained during the GLOBE campaign. These measurements are complemented by mesoscale model outputs from WRF data, coming from the X-Wakes project, and reanalysis data from ERA5. Together, these sources provide information at both the turbine and atmospheric levels, forming a good foundation for evaluating the coupled model under CBL conditions.

3.1 Wind Farm Cluster Layout and Wind Turbine types

As mentioned above, the N4 cluster consists of three wind farms, with Amrumbank West—the northernmost, serving as the focus of this study. It comprises 80 Siemens SWT-3.6-120 offshore wind turbines, each with a rated capacity of

3.6 MW, a rotor diameter of 120 m, and a hub height of 89 m. The turbines are arranged in a regular grid with approximately $5 D$ spacing in the north–south direction and $7 D$ in the east–west direction, where D denotes the rotor diameter. The turbine cut-in and cut-out wind speeds are 4.0 m/s and 25 m/s, respectively.

Although the analysis in this thesis focuses solely on Amrumbank West, the neighboring wind farms in the N4 cluster can influence the flow conditions around it and are therefore important to describe. South of Amrumbank West lies the Nordsee Ost wind farm, equipped with 48 Senvion 6.2M126 turbines, each with a rated power of 6.15 MW, a rotor diameter of 126 m, and a hub height of 96.5 m. The cut-in and cut-out wind speeds are 3.5 m/s and 25 m/s, respectively. Notably, two blade types are used, LM and RE, introducing variability in power and thrust characteristics. This heterogeneity also contributed to the decision to focus on Amrumbank West, where a single turbine type is used throughout, thereby simplifying the analysis and improving the consistency of the power model evaluation.

Further south is the Meerwind Süd/Ost wind farm, consisting of 80 Siemens SWT-3.6-120 turbines, identical in design to those at Amrumbank West but arranged in a less dense layout. An overview of the turbine specifications is provided in Table 5. Figure 18 presents the layout of the N4 cluster, with each wind farm distinguished by marker type and turbine model.

Table 5: Specifications of turbine types used in the study

Turbine Features	Siemens SWT-3.6-120	Senvion 6.2M126
Rotor diameter [m]	120	126
Hub height [m]	89	96.5
Rated power [MW]	3.6	6.15
Cut-in wind speed [m/s]	4.0	3.5
Cut-out wind speed [m/s]	33	25
Number of turbines	80	23(LM) + 25(RE)

Figure 18: Layout of the N4 cluster, consisting of three wind farms: Amrumbank West, Nordsee Ost, and Meerwind Süd/Ost, each highlighted by a distinct marker. The color code represents the turbine type.

3.2 Data Sources

To support this study, a comprehensive observational dataset from the OWA GLOBE campaign was utilized, comprising SCADA data, lidar measurements, and meteorological mast observations. In addition to these measurements, mesoscale model outputs from WRF and reanalysis data from ERA5 were also added.

A meteorological mast is installed near the southernmost turbine of the Nordsee Ost wind farm, as shown in Figure 18. This mast is equipped with a set of sensors mounted at various heights, i.e., at 32 m, 48 m, 70 m, 92 m, and 96 to capture vertical profiles of some key atmospheric parameters. The most relevant variables recorded are wind speed, wind direction, temperature, pressure, and humidity. These measurements are used as 10-minute averaged values and are critical for understanding the local wind field and thermodynamic structure at the lowest part of the ABL, up to 100 meters in height. Of particular importance is the inverse Obukhov length parameter (L_{92}^{-1}), derived at both 32 m and 92 m height, with the latter serving as a key parameter to access atmospheric stability (restricted to the SL). This parameter will be essential in the following analysis to assess stability conditions at or near hub height. This will be explained in more detail in a later section. Mast data is available from August 9, 2021 until February 13, 2023.

As part of the GloBE campaign, multiple lidar systems were deployed offshore,

including dual-Doppler scanning lidars for wind field reconstruction and a floating profiling lidar for atmospheric characterization. For this study, a single *WindCube 200* lidar, provided by *Fraunhofer IWES* as part of the *X-Wakes* collaboration, is of particular importance, as it, together with the profiling lidar, delivers boundary layer height estimates that are central to the stability analysis conducted later in this work. The location of this lidar is marked on Figure 18 by the grey-circled turbine. The dataset covers the period from August 15, 2021, to April 26, 2022.

Additionally to the measured data, mesoscale model output was included from both WRF simulations and ERA5 reanalysis data. The former, WRF, offers the highest spatial and temporal resolution, with output available every 10 minutes and a horizontal resolution of 1–3 km. However, in this study, the WRF data is provided at a single, fixed location.

The WRF model output includes a comprehensive set of atmospheric variables at multiple vertical levels, ranging from 50 m to 500 m above ground level, namely at 50, 75, 90, 100, 150, 200, 250, and 500 meters. Key variables include wind speed (WS), wind direction (WD), temperature (T), specific humidity (QVAPOR), and turbulent kinetic energy (TKE), all resolved at heights relevant to wind energy applications. In addition, surface-related parameters such as skin temperature (TSK), 2-meter temperature (T2), 10-meter wind speed and direction (WS10, WD10), surface pressure (PSFC), friction velocity (UST), inverse Obukhov length (RMOL), surface roughness length (ZNT), and planetary boundary layer height (PBLH) are provided. This high-resolution and vertically detailed WRF output is particularly useful for assessing atmospheric stability and wind shear in offshore environments. In particular, the temperature profiles will be of key importance later in this work for conditioning on CBL states. WRF data is available for the years 2019-2022.

In contrast, ERA5 offers hourly data at a global scale with a coarser horizontal resolution of approximately 31 km ($0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$). Despite this lower resolution, ERA5 provides valuable information at higher atmospheric levels through 37 pressure levels ranging from 1000 hPa to 1 hPa, making it highly complementary to the WRF data. ERA5 data is freely available online. The exact location for ERA5 data extraction is determined based on Figure 19, which displays the N4 Cluster region. For this study, the grid point at latitude 54.5° and longitude 7.75° is selected for further analysis.

Figure 19: Different possible ERA5 data extraction points. For the study at hand, the grid point at lat 54.5° and lon 7.75° is selected.

Lastly, turbine SCADA data is used and plays a central role in the experimental validation of the developed power models, which will be detailed in the following section. SCADA data is available for the Amrumbank West and Nordsee Ost wind farms and provides key turbine-level parameters at a 10-minute resolution. The most critical variable is the *Active Power*, recorded individually for each turbine. Additional relevant parameters include the *Nacelle Yaw Direction*, the *Site Curtailment Power Limitation*, which indirectly indicates the number of operational turbines, and the *Farm-Average Wind Speed*, calculated as the average rotor-equivalent wind speed of the 10% most efficient turbines.

Table 6: Data availability across different data sources

Type of Data	Start Date	End Date
Mast data	2021-08-09	2023-02-13
ABL height data	2021-08-15	2022-04-26
LiDAR data	2021-08-15	2023-02-13
WRF data	2019-01-01	2022-12-31
SCADA data	2021-01-01	2022-12-31
Common period	2021-08-15	2022-04-26

The availability of high-resolution observational data at Amrumbank West, including SCADA, lidar, mast, and mesoscale model outputs, provides a strong foundation for investigating wind farm–atmosphere interactions.

4 Convective Boundary Layer Filtering

This chapter outlines the filtering strategy used to extract timestamps representative of convective boundary layer (CBL) conditions, which are essential for consistent evaluation of ABL–wind farm interactions in offshore environments. As discussed in Section 2.2.1 and Section 2.2.2, the MBL at the offshore location of the N4 cluster is typically weakly unstable or near-neutral, with seasonal and advective influences prevailing over diurnal heating cycles due to the high thermal inertia of the sea surface.

Despite their relative scarcity offshore, CBL regimes are valuable for model development because their enhanced turbulence promotes faster wake recovery and clearer microscale–mesoscale coupling. Moreover, their well-mixed structure offers a simplified thermodynamic reference for model validation.

To identify such conditions, a two-step filtering approach is adopted: (1) a stability-based filter using the Ri_b to identify well-mixed or unstable stratification across the rotor disk, and (2) a potential temperature difference (PTD) filter to confirm vertical mixing. The methodology uses both meteorological mast observations and high-resolution WRF output, with further details and statistical evaluation presented in the sections below.

4.1 CBL-Conditions

This subsection outlines a two-step filtering approach to identify periods representative of CBL conditions. The procedure starts with SL stability metrics, such as the Obukhov length, but due to their inconsistency across heights and datasets, a more robust metric, the bulk Richardson number, is adopted. This metric captures vertical gradients over the rotor-swept layer. Finally, a PTD filter between fixed heights is applied to further isolate well-mixed, convective conditions. Each step is detailed in the following subsections.

4.1.1 Stability Filter

This filtering step targets the thermodynamic stratification in the lower ABL to isolate periods characterized by buoyancy-driven mixing—typical of weakly unstable or near-neutral marine conditions. Initially, surface-layer metrics such as the Obukhov length are assessed across WRF and met mast datasets. However, notable inconsistencies between sources and measurement heights motivate a shift to the bulk Richardson number, which offers a vertically integrated and more robust representation of atmospheric stability over the rotor-swept layer.

Atmospheric Stability Classification Challenges

Classifying the atmosphere into a specific stability regime presents challenges, particularly when drawing from multiple data sources such as WRF model output and meteorological mast observations. Each dataset offers different stability

indicators, often derived at different heights or based on slightly different assumptions, which can lead to inconsistencies. In what follows, a small note on how to deal with this is given.

As discussed in Section 2.1.1, atmospheric stability can be assessed using various metrics, including the Obukhov length L and the Richardson number Ri . Stability-related parameters are available across different datasets. For example, the meteorological mast provides inverse Obukhov lengths at both 32 m and 92 m, with the 92 m measurement being more relevant due to its proximity to hub height. The WRF data also includes the inverse Obukhov length, labeled $RMOL$, though the exact height at which it is reported remains unknown at the time of writing. Figure 20 shows the distribution of grouped stability classes, i.e. stable, neutral, and unstable, based on the Monin-Obukhov length, as derived from WRF data and met mast observations at 32 m and 92 m. The classification follows the scheme proposed by Peña et al. [8], as detailed in Table 1, with grouping of the stable and unstable classes.

Figure 20: Distribution of grouped atmospheric stability classes (stable, neutral, unstable) based on the Monin–Obukhov length L , as derived from the WRF model and met mast observations at 32 m and 92 m.

As shown in Figure 20, unstable conditions dominate across all sources, which aligns with expectations for the site and period considered. Although the overall distributions appear to indicate a relatively good agreement between datasets, this impression is somewhat misleading. In reality, notable differences are observed when comparing the stability classifications from the WRF model and the met mast at matching timestamps. These inconsistencies are illustrated in Figure 21, which presents the confusion matrices comparing WRF-derived classifications with those from the met mast at 32 m and 92 m. Particularly near the class boundaries, disagreements are common, as many cases labeled as neutral or stable by one dataset are marked as unstable by the other.

These differences can be partly explained by vertical gradients in wind and potential temperature, which arise from the advection of air masses over a sea surface with a different temperature. Given the limited depth of the ABL in such cases,

these gradients lead to variations in stability classification across different heights, underscoring the limitations of using single-height metrics like the Monin-Obukhov length. The confusion matrices suggest that the WRF-based Monin-Obukhov length is most likely representative of conditions near 32 m, rather than 92 m, as it shows greater agreement with the mast-derived classifications at the lower height.

Figure 21: Comparison of stability classification from WRF data with met mast observations at 32 m and 92 m heights. The heatmap values represent the percentage of total cases classified in each category. Diagonal boxes represent agreement between the two sources.

These findings underscore a larger challenge in classifying stability for wind energy applications. Traditional point-based metrics like the Obukhov length are highly localized and mainly useful in the SL but fail to represent the thermodynamic structure of the full atmospheric boundary layer, which is of major importance in this work. To overcome this limitation, we adopt the Ri_b as the primary stability metric in this thesis.

The Bulk Richardson Number

The Bulk Richardson Number (Ri_b), introduced earlier in Section 2.1.3, incorporates wind and temperature gradients over a vertical layer, providing a more integrated and physically representative measure of atmospheric stability. This makes it particularly suitable for evaluating conditions relevant to wind turbine operation, where inflow dynamics are shaped by the structure of the lower atmosphere.

Since the met mast data extends only up to 92 m, the evaluation of Ri_b is based on WRF model output. To ensure the metric captures the stability of the air volume interacting with the turbines, it is computed between 50 m and 200 m above sea level. The lower boundary is chosen to minimize the influence of near-surface effects such as roughness, heterogeneity, and local heat fluxes, i.e. to be outside the SL. The upper boundary encompasses the full vertical extent of the rotor tips for both turbines considered: 149 m for the Siemens 3.6 MW and 158 m for the Senvion 6.2 MW, as specified in Table 5. This vertical interval enables a stabil-

ity classification that better reflects the atmospheric conditions across the rotor disk, offering a more robust value for assessing turbine performance under varying stratification regimes.

Figure 22 visualized the comparison between evaluation of the Ri_b reference height and 100 meters and 200 meters. For Figure 22a, the reference height is chosen to be 10 meters whereas for Figure 22b, the reference height is 50 meter. The color code of the plots represent the WRF-modeled ABL height. The vertical and horizontal dotted lines represent the transition from one stability class to another according to Ri_B -based stability classification introduced in Section 2.1.3. Stable conditions are associated with lower ABL heights, as shown by the blue cluster in the upper-right corner of both plots. The figures highlight the height-dependent nature of stability: situations that appear unstable at 100 m often become stable at 200 m, while the reverse is uncommon. This indicates a general trend of increasing stability with height. In the left panel, which uses 10 m as the reference height, surface-layer influences become apparent. Some cases indicate greater stability in the bulk layer between 10 and 100 m than between 10 and 200 m. This may result from surface effects or the development of a new ABL regime as the SBL begins to grow. To avoid having surface effects impacting the stability evaluation, 50 m inputs are used as a reference height.

Figure 22: Comparison of (Ri_b) evaluation at at 100 meter and 200 meter height with reference at (a) 10 meters and (b) 50 meters. The color code corresponds with WRF-modeled planetary boundary layer height.

4.1.2 Potential Temperature Difference (PTD) Filter

The second condition in the filtering procedure relies on the potential temperature difference (PTD) between two predefined heights. This PTD-based method, introduced earlier in the literature review (Section 2.2.2), is used here to identify well-mixed ABL regimes. In this study, the PTD is computed between 50 m and 250 m, following the original formulation by Liu et al. [11]. This height range is well aligned with the rotor-swept area of the turbines considered and is compatible with the vertical resolution of the WRF dataset.

From Temperature to Potential Temperature

As introduced in Section 3, the WRF dataset provides temperature at multiple pre-defined heights up to 500 m, including near-surface values. To compute potential temperature, the standard definition is applied as given by Equation (48). More details on this, reference is made to Section 2.1.2.

$$\theta = T \left(\frac{P_0}{P} \right)^\kappa \quad (48)$$

Since pressure values at model height levels are not directly available in the WRF output, they are reconstructed using the hydrostatic approximation under a dry adiabatic lapse rate, as described in Equation (49). This method simplifies the vertical structure of the atmosphere by assuming a constant lapse rate, although in reality, the lapse rate can vary with atmospheric stability. A more refined reconstruction could therefore adjust the lapse rate dynamically based on the Monin–Obukhov number provided in the WRF output. The surface pressure and 2-meter temperature, denoted as P_{surface} and T_{surface} , are directly available as the variables PSFC and T2, while temperature values at higher levels are retrieved from channels such as T-50, T-100, etc. The hydrostatic formulation relies on several physical constants: the reference pressure P_0 , gravitational acceleration g , the specific gas constant for dry air R_d , the standard lapse rate Γ , and the Poisson constant $\kappa = R_d/c_p$, with c_p being the specific heat at constant pressure. These parameters allow for the computation of pressure and potential temperature profiles at each model level. An overview of the constants and their values is provided in Table 7.

$$P(z) = P_{\text{surface}} \left(\frac{T_{\text{surface}} - \Gamma z}{T_{\text{surface}}} \right)^{\frac{g}{R_d \Gamma}}, \quad (49)$$

Table 7: Constants used in thermodynamic calculations

Parameter	Value
Reference pressure P_0	100000 Pa
Dry Adiabatic Lapse rate Γ	0.0065 K/m
Gas constant for dry air R_d	287.0 J/(kg·K)
Specific heat at constant pressure C_p	1004.0 J/(kg·K)
Gravitational acceleration g	9.81 m/s ²
$\kappa = R_d/C_p$	≈ 0.2857

Final Regime Classification Using the PTD Method

Once the potential temperature has been computed at the relevant vertical levels, the PTD method is applied to classify the ABL regime. Given the marine environment of the study area, the threshold value σ for regime identification is set to 0.2 K as suggested by Liu et al. [11]. This leads to the classification criteria outlined in Equation (50).

$$\text{PTD} = \theta_{z_{\text{upper}}} - \theta_{z_{\text{lower}}} = \begin{cases} < -0.2, & \text{CBL (unstable)} \\ > +0.2, & \text{SBL (stable)} \\ \in [-0.2, +0.2], & \text{NRL (neutral)} \end{cases} \quad (50)$$

Figure 23 illustrates the distribution of PTD under different atmospheric conditions. Panel (a) shows the distribution for the full WRF dataset, excluding cases labeled as 'Undefined' in the SL stability classification by Peña et al. [8]. Panel (b) shows the same but additionally for a subset of the data filtered using the bulk Richardson number criterion $Ri_b^{200\text{m}} < 0.1$, which isolates dynamically unstable or near-neutral atmospheric conditions over the rotor area.

From Figure 23a, it is evident that the full dataset exhibits a pronounced upper tail with $\text{PTD} > 0.2\text{K}$, associated with a greater presence of near-stable, stable, and very stable cases. Although applying a PTD threshold of 0.2K is intended to isolate convective conditions, it does not fully exclude stable SL conditions, as seen by the presence of stable classes even for PTD values below this threshold. The additional application of the Ri_b filter in Figure 23b significantly reduces these residual stable cases, leading to a subset more representative of convective or well-mixed conditions.

It can be observed that for σ equal to 0.2K , almost no cases would be categorized as CBL. While increasing the CBL threshold (e.g., to -0.1K) could increase the number of detected CBL cases, doing so symmetrically would narrow the NRL classification (e.g., to $-0.1\text{K} < \sigma < 0.1\text{K}$) and exclude a substantial number of relevant neutral SL cases. Both the CBL and NRL represent well-mixed, non-stable conditions that are central to this study. Although the NRL forms during the night, it is a residual layer originating from the daytime CBL and therefore relevant for this study. Since additional filtering steps are applied later, both regimes are retained for the subsequent analysis using the original 0.2K PTD threshold and $Ri_b^{200\text{m}} < 0.1$ filtering.

Figure 23: Distribution of PTD between 50 and 200 m. (a) Full dataset grouped by surface-layer stability class. (b) Subset of cases filtered for bulk Richardson number $Ri_b^{200\text{m}} < 0.1$.

4.2 Statistical Analysis of Filtered CBL Cases

This subsection provides a brief overview of the most relevant statistics and features of the filtered cases, i.e., those classified as either CBL or RNL. After applying the filtering procedure, approximately 40.0 % of the total cases are retained, spanning a range of surface-layer-defined stability classes. This percentage is slightly lower than the combined frequency of ABL regimes reported by Liu et al. [11], who found average daily occurrences of 30–35 % for CBL and 20–25 % for RNL, respectively. Table 8 summarizes the number of filtered cases per stability class, along with the number of unique days over which these cases are distributed. It is evident that the majority of retained cases correspond to unstable and neutral conditions, while only a limited number of stable cases pass the filtering criteria.

Table 8: Number of cases and unique days per stability class (WRF data, 2021–2022)

Stability Class	Number of Cases	Unique Days
Neutral (N)	5987	182
Near Unstable (NU)	7657	228
Unstable (U)	8232	251
Very Unstable (VU)	7495	246
Near Stable (NS)	133	36
Stable (S)	47	10
Very Stable (VS)	20	5

Figure 24 shows the total number of cases as a function of the hour of the day. A weak diurnal cycle can be observed, with a higher number of cases in the afternoon and evening and a noticeable dip during the night. This pattern aligns with the typical formation timing of the different boundary layer regimes, as discussed in Section 2.2.1. The nighttime dip can be attributed to the increased occurrence of the SBL, particularly during the later hours of the night, when the stable boundary layer is well-developed and its height lies within the PTD evaluation range.

Figure 24: Hourly distribution of identified cases, showing a weak diurnal cycle with fewer cases at night due to increased SBL occurrence.

Figure 25 shows the yearly distribution of the filtered cases, color-coded by SL-detected stability class. A seasonal pattern is observed, as highlighted by the

black line, which represents a fitted oscillation to the bars. Due to the high heat capacity of seawater, this cycle is delayed compared to typical patterns observed over land. Peak CBL conditions occur in late summer and autumn, when the ocean retains substantial thermal energy. During this period, colder autumn air masses moving over the still-warm sea surface create favorable conditions for CBL development. Conversely, in late winter and spring, the sea surface remains cold while warmer air masses move overhead, promoting stable stratification and reducing the likelihood of CBL formation.

Figure 25: Yearly distribution of the filtered cases colorcoded by the SL-detected stability based on WRF data

Figure 26 shows the wind rose of the filtered dataset, with wind speed color-coded in 5 m/s bins and divided into 18 directional sectors of 20°. The figure indicates that the predominant wind direction is west-northwest, while easterly directions occur much less frequently. This directional bias is important for the subsequent analysis, as it informs which wind directions are most relevant for the case study. Further details on this will be discussed in a later section.

Figure 26: Wind rose of the filtered dataset.

Lastly, Figure 27 shows the distribution of ABL height for all filtered cases. As the ABL height, and by extension, the inversion height of the potential temperature profile—is hypothesized to influence the coupling strength between microscale and mesoscale power models, its distribution is examined under filtered conditions. Subfigure (a) presents the histogram, and subfigure (b) shows the corresponding kernel density estimate, both color-coded by the SL-defined stability class. Most ABL heights fall within the range of 300 to 1500 m, with a long tail extending toward 2000 m. Section 4.2 further illustrates that stable conditions are typically associated with lower ABL heights, while neutral to unstable conditions span a broader and generally higher range. As the focus of this analysis lies primarily on near-neutral conditions, the corresponding kernel density estimate is highlighted, showing a distinct distribution between 300 and 1600 m. Similar ABL height distributions under convective to near-neutral conditions have also been reported by Liu et al. [11].

Figure 27: Distribution of ABL height for the filtered cases. **Left:** Stacked histogram showing the frequency of ABL heights for different SL stability classes. **Right:** Kernel density estimates of ABL height distributions, separated by SL stability class.

5 Rampanelli Potential Temperature Profile Fitting

As mentioned before, the input to MSC models must reflect a thorough understanding of atmospheric characteristics. These include the inversion height l , inversion strength $\Delta\theta$, free atmospheric lapse rate γ , and the reference potential temperature θ_{00} . These variables are essential for evaluating how mesoscale atmospheric conditions influence microscale power output.

The literature review provided an overview of various approaches to represent the vertical structure of the atmosphere, ranging from zero-order and first-order jump models to continuous analytical profiles. Particular focus was placed on the mathematical fitting algorithm developed by Rampanelli and Zardi [19], which uses basis functions $f(z)$ and $g(z)$, scaled by parameters a and b , to capture both the sharp transition across the inversion layer and the asymptotic growth of potential temperature in the free atmosphere. The full expression (see Equation (16)) connects the parameters a , b , θ_m , l , and Δh to physically meaningful quantities: the inversion height l , inversion strength $\Delta\theta$, reference potential temperature θ_{00} , and lapse rate γ .

In the present work, the Rampanelli fitting approach is adapted for application to a blended profile constructed from WRF and ERA5 data. This section describes the implementation methodology, including preprocessing steps and constraint formulation, and evaluates the accuracy of the resulting fits. Emphasis is placed on distinguishing between typical inversion profiles and encroachment conditions, and on examining how the derived parameters differ between these two atmospheric regimes.

5.1 Implementation approach

In the work of Rampanelli and Zardi, airborne measurements, such as those obtained from meteorological balloons with high vertical resolution, were used to apply the fitting algorithm. In the present study, however, such airborne measurements are not available. Instead, a combination of near-surface and moderately resolved WRF data is used together with high-resolution ERA5 data to approximate the vertical structure needed for the fitting procedure.

To construct a continuous and realistic potential temperature profile, the WRF data is used up to approximately 500 meters, capturing the near-surface structure, while ERA5 data is used to characterize the upper atmosphere. A linear blending region is introduced between 450 and 700 meters to ensure a smooth transition between the two datasets. This approach addresses the possible mismatch between the *WRF* and *ERA5* data around the transition height. By blending the profiles within this range, the method avoids discontinuities that could arise from switching abruptly between the two data sources. This combined profile is then interpolated using a monotonic PCHIP interpolator to maintain the physical characteristics of the stratification.

To reduce numerical noise and enforce physical realism, the vertical gradient of the potential temperature is smoothed using a Savitzky–Golay filter. Moreover, a constant free-atmosphere lapse rate (γ) is imposed above 2500 meters to reflect the typically linear stratification of the upper atmosphere. This threshold is chosen based on the analysis in Section 4, which shows that the highest WRF-detected ABL heights range between 1500 and 2000 meters. Hence, it is reasonable to assume that heights above 2500 meters lie within the free atmosphere. The resulting smoothed and physically consistent profile is then used as input for the Rampanelli and Zardi fitting algorithm.

The fitting algorithm is implemented using a weighted nonlinear least-squares optimization. Physical bounds are imposed on the parameters, and a soft constraint anchors the inversion-layer center height (l) near external estimates of boundary layer height from WRF, ERA5, and lidar. The confidence in this constraint depends on the vertical spread of these estimates. The smaller the spread, the higher the assumed accuracy, and thus the stronger the constraint weight.

The fitting returns estimates of the mixed-layer potential temperature (θ_m), the scaling parameters (a and b), the entrainment-layer center height (l), and its thickness (Δh). Derived quantities such as the inversion base (h_0), the inversion top (h_2), inversion strength ($\Delta\theta$), and the free-atmospheric lapse rate (γ) are also computed. A coefficient of determination (R^2) is reported to evaluate the accuracy of the fit.

5.2 Fitting Results

The fitting algorithm is applied to the filtered WRF data, based on the criteria outlined in Section 4. To reduce visual clutter, the results are shown for a smaller subset of timestamps. Nevertheless, the selected number of profiles is statistically representative, as including additional timestamps does not significantly alter the statistical conclusions presented.

Figure 29 shows the fitted potential temperature profiles for the processed timestamps. By using the a -parameter in the fitting procedure, a distinction is made between standard inversion profiles and encroachment profiles, which are shown in blue and green, respectively. For each class, one representative profile is highlighted using a thicker line.

Figure 28

In order to quantify the goodness of fit, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is calculated using the predicted profile and the observed data. This metric reflects how well the fitted profile captures the variance in the observed potential temperature profile. The R^2 value is defined in Equation (51), where θ_i are the measured potential temperatures, $\hat{\theta}_i$ are the predicted values from the fitted model, and $\bar{\theta}$ is the mean of the observed potential temperature.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\theta_i - \hat{\theta}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (\theta_i - \bar{\theta})^2}. \quad (51)$$

Figure 29 shows a normalized stacked histogram of R^2 values. The distribution distinguishes between encroachment cases and normal conditions, demonstrating that the fitting quality remains high across both regimes. It can be stated that the fitting algorithm reproduces the modeled WRF and ERA5 profiles quite well, as the R^2 values have a minimum of approximately 0.925, with a progressively increasing probability density toward 1.

Figure 29: Visual comparison of fitted and observed potential temperature profiles along with their corresponding R^2 values. The histogram is normalized and stacked, separating encroachment conditions from normal conditions.

To illustrate the goodness of the fitting approach, Figure 31 presents two examples of the Rampanelli and Zardi potential temperature profile fitting: a typical inversion case (left) and an encroachment case (right). In both panels, yellow markers represent WRF model data and green markers denote ERA5 reanalysis data. The red line shows the fitted potential temperature profile. It should be noted that, for illustrative purposes, the profile within each condition with a high R^2 values was selected.

Key ABL characteristics are annotated for each case. The reference potential temperature θ_{00} is shown as a vertical black dashed line. The fitted ABL height h_1 is marked with a horizontal solid blue line, and is compared to the WRF and ERA5 modelled ABL heights (yellow and green dashed lines, respectively). The inversion base h_0 and inversion top h_2 are indicated by horizontal blue dashed and dotted lines.

In the left panel (typical inversion), the inversion strength $\Delta\theta$, the inversion layer thickness Δh , and the free atmospheric lapse rate γ are all illustrated, characterizing the stratification above the ABL. These parameters highlight the algorithm's ability to capture the key thermal features of atmosphere.

Figure 30: Rampanelli and Zardi potential temperature profile fits for two example cases: a typical inversion profile (left) and an encroachment profile (right).

In what follows, the results of the ABL-characteristic parameters are analyzed by examining their statistical distributions. Where relevant, comparisons are made between encroachment and non-encroachment (i.e., typical inversion) conditions. The analysis begins with the estimated ABL height (l), followed by the inversion strength ($\Delta\theta$), the free atmospheric lapse rate (γ), and the reference potential temperature (θ_{00}).

ABL-height estimation

Figures 31 and 32 present comparisons between the ABL height l estimated from the Rampanelli fitting procedure and the model-diagnosed boundary layer heights from WRF and ERA5, respectively, across the processed timestamps. In both cases, the data generally follow a positive trend, with individual deviations depending on the stability regime (indicated by the color of the markers, corresponding to the SL stability class).

For the WRF comparison (Figure 31), the data show an approximately linear relationship, with a linear regression (not shown) yielding a slope of 0.88 and an R^2 value of 0.54. This suggests that the Rampanelli-derived heights tend to slightly underestimate WRF-modeled values, though with moderate correlation.

The ERA5 comparison (Figure 32) shows a similar trend but with significantly more scatter. The fitted line (also not shown) has a slope of 0.53 and an intercept of 289.46, indicating that Rampanelli tends to overestimate ABL height at low values and underestimate it at high values relative to ERA5. The low $R^2 = 0.27$ reflects a weaker agreement compared to WRF.

Figure 31: Comparison between the ABL height estimated from the Rampanelli fitting and the WRF-modeled ABL height across all processed timestamps. Colors denote the SL stability class.

Figure 32: Comparison between the ABL height estimated from the Rampanelli fitting and the ERA5-modeled ABL height across all processed timestamps. Colors denote the SL stability class.

Free Atmospheric Lapse Rate

Figure 33 presents the distribution of free-atmospheric lapse rates γ . Most values lie between 0.002 and 0.008 K m^{-1} , with a peak near 0.005 K m^{-1} , reflecting typical thermal stratification above the inversion layer. These values are consistent with those reported in the literature. For instance, Rampanelli et al. [19] reported lapse rates ranging from 1.5 to almost 6.0 K km^{-1} based on airborne observations based θ -fitting, while Liu and Liang [11] found slightly lower free-tropospheric θ -gradients using global radiosonde and reanalysis data.

Panel (a) shows a stacked histogram of γ values, while panel (b) displays the corresponding kernel density estimates (KDEs) for the dominant SL-defined stability classes. In both panels, values are grouped by SL-defined stability class. This classification highlights how the distribution of free-atmosphere lapse rates varies slightly with near-surface atmospheric conditions for the analysed cases. The International Standard Atmosphere (ISA) lapse rate of 6.5 K km^{-1} (0.0065 K m^{-1}) is overlaid as a reference. Note, however, that this value refers to the lapse rate of actual temperature in the ABL, not of potential temperature in the FA. In contrast, potential temperature gradients in the FA typically increase more gradually,

so slightly lower values than the ISA standard are expected under normal conditions. For the cases analyzed here, the distribution peaks around 0.005 K m^{-1} . More stable surface-layer conditions are associated with higher gradient values (up to 0.007 K m^{-1}), while more unstable conditions show gradients as low as 0.002 K m^{-1} .

Figure 33: Distribution of free-atmospheric lapse rates (γ) based on Rampanelli profile fitting. (a) Histogram grouped by surface-layer-defined stability classes. (b) Normalized KDEs per class, with the ISA lapse rate shown as reference.

Additionally, Figure 34 shows the distribution of γ under encroachment and normal conditions. It can be observed that for normal conditions, the distribution of γ is centered around lower values, indicating a weaker stratification of the free atmosphere. In contrast, encroachment profiles are associated with higher lapse rates, consistent with stronger stability aloft. As a result, the convective boundary layer has a harder time entraining air from above and therefore grows more slowly.

Figure 34: Distribution of the free-atmosphere lapse rate γ under encroachment and normal conditions. Encroachment cases are associated with higher lapse rates.

The Inversion Strength $\Delta\theta$

The next atmospheric parameter examined is the inversion strength, $\Delta\theta$. Figure 35 shows the KDE of $\Delta\theta$ for all fitted profiles (black dashed line). When categorizing the data by encroachment and non-encroachment conditions, a clear distinction is observed: lower inversion strengths are more common under encroachment conditions, whereas higher values are associated with profiles that show a clear capping inversion.

These findings are consistent with those reported by Rampanelli et al. [19], who, based on θ -profile fitting of airborne measurements, observed inversion strengths up to 15 K, with the weakest inversions (around 1 K) occurring under encroachment conditions.

Figure 35: Kernel density estimates of inversion strength $\Delta\theta$, categorized by profile type. Encroachment profiles tend to show lower inversion strengths, while normal temperature profiles exhibit higher values, consistent with a well-defined capping inversion.

Reference Potential Temperature

Lastly, Figure 36 presents the distribution of the reference potential temperature θ_{00} for both encroachment and normal conditions (i.e., a combination of encroachment and entrainment). It can be observed that θ_{00} values under encroachment conditions are generally lower than those under normal conditions. As discussed in Section 2.2.4, entrainment is characterized by the exchange of air across the inversion layer, allowing warmer air from the FA aloft to be mixed into the ABL. Due to strong turbulent mixing in the ML, this leads to an increase in potential temperature. In contrast, under pure encroachment conditions, this heat exchange with the FA is absent, and the only heat source is the sensible heat flux from the surface. As a result, the θ_{00} values remain generally lower.

Figure 36: Kernel density estimates of reference potential temperature θ_{00} , categorized by profile type. Encroachment profiles show lower reference values compared to normal θ -profiles.

6 Power Modeling Methodology

This section presents the modeling approaches used to estimate wind farm power output in the N4 Cluster, focusing on Amrumbank West. The analysis is built on the `PyWake` framework [55], which enables fast, flexible simulation of turbine interactions using engineering models of varying complexity. These microscale models approximate key wake effects and local blockage, offering computational efficiency for power estimation under different wind conditions.

However, traditional microscale approaches are limited in their ability to represent large-scale atmospheric influences, such as pressure gradients, gravity waves, and global blockage, which can significantly impact wind farm performance. To overcome this, an in-house MLC model has been developed, coupling microscale wake dynamics with mesoscale flow features. In what follows, the different models, both microscale and mesoscale, are introduced, along with their key characteristics.

6.1 PyWake Micro-Scale Models

Within the `PyWake` framework, wind farm flow models are initialized by specifying a set of modular components that define how wakes, turbulence, and turbine interactions are modeled. While these models share a common input structure, they differ significantly in their physical treatment of key flow phenomena—particularly in whether they account only for downstream wake effects or also include upstream influence and blockage. Moreover, the way these effects are coupled—either sequentially or fully iteratively—further distinguishes them. This modularity allows users to tailor simulations to site-specific conditions and focus on the most relevant physical processes. This is of particular importance for this thesis, as it enables the setup of consistent model benchmarks and the tuning of wake parameters using SCADA data.

All `PyWake` models require several key inputs. First, a `Site` object provides the wind resource data, including wind speed, wind direction, and turbulence intensity. Second, a `WindTurbines` object defines the turbine geometry, along with the power and thrust curves, and specifies the wind farm or cluster layout. Third, a `wake_deficitModel` must be selected from the available models introduced in Section 2.3. This model determines both the magnitude of the velocity deficit and the shape of the wake (e.g., Gaussian, top-hat), based on the turbine's characteristics and downstream distance. As this study involves multiple interacting turbines, it is also essential to provide a `superpositionModel` that combines the effects of overlapping wakes. Furthermore, a `rotorAvgModel` must be specified to define how wind speed is averaged over the rotor area, and a `turbulenceModel` is required to represent the increase in turbulence caused by wake interactions. The choice of the latter component, together with the selection of the `wake_deficitModel`, is of particular importance in this study, as both will be tuned to the wind farm under investigation. This tuning is critical for accurately capturing flow behavior in dense wind farm configurations and for calibrating the

model against available SCADA data in the power comparison analysis. More details about this are provided in Section 7. An overview of all required inputs is provided in Table 10.

PropagateDownwind

`PropagateDownwind` is the most basic flow model available in PyWake. It simulates wake effects by sequentially propagating deficits only in the downstream direction. This means that each turbine affects only those turbines located downstream, and upstream interactions are not considered. Because it does not model blockage or require iterative solving, it has low computational cost and is well-suited for fast layout optimization and AEP calculations. It uses only the standard input components described above.

All2AllIterative

`All2AllIterative` is the most comprehensive and physically detailed model in the PyWake framework. It captures both wake and blockage effects in all directions through a fully coupled iterative scheme. Unlike simpler models, this approach accounts for mutual interactions between all turbines, both upstream and downstream at each iteration. This enables a highly accurate representation of the wind field, which is particularly important in complex or dense wind farm configurations. In addition to the standard PyWake inputs, this model requires a dedicated `blockage_deficitModel` to explicitly simulate the upstream (blockage) component of the flow deficit, and a convergence criterion (e.g., `convergence_tolerance = 0.001` m/s) to define when the iterative process ends. Although computationally demanding, `All2AllIterative` provides the most physically consistent results available within the PyWake framework. It is therefore best suited for detailed research applications, sensitivity analyses, and validation against high-fidelity simulations such as CFD or LES.

PropagateUpDownIterative

`PropagateUpDownIterative` is an intermediate-level wind farm model that combines key features of both `PropagateDownwind` and `All2AllIterative`. It extends the downstream-only approach of `PropagateDownwind` by introducing an iterative solver capable of capturing upstream blockage effects—without requiring an explicit `blockage_deficitModel`. Instead, the upstream influence is handled implicitly through the iterative recalculation of the flow field. This model retains the same input structure as `PropagateDownwind`, while internally introducing convergence logic (e.g., via `convergence_tolerance`) to ensure the flow field stabilizes. While less computationally intensive than `All2AllIterative`, it significantly improves accuracy in more dense wind farms where upstream deceleration, i.e., blockage effects, plays a non-negligible role. This makes it a suitable choice for the wind farm cluster study in this thesis, where it is important to balance accuracy with reasonable computation time.

Object	Description
site	Wind conditions: speed, direction, turbulence
windTurbines	Wind turbine and farm characteristics
wake_deficitModel	Defines downstream wind speed loss
superpositionModel	Combines multiple wake deficits
rotorAvgModel	Computes rotor-avg wind speed
deflectionModel	Simulates yaw/sheer-induced shift
turbulenceModel	Models wake-added turbulence
blockage_deficitModel	Defines upstream wind loss
convergence_tolerance	Stop criterion for iterations

Table 9: Typical input objects for PyWake flow models with brief descriptions.

6.2 Micro-Scale Power Model Choice and Case Study Inputs

With the various models introduced, a selection is made for those used in the power comparison study. The required inputs for configuring the micro-scale wake models to specific study cases are summarized below.

Model Choice

For this thesis, both the `PropagateDownwind` and `PropagateUpDownIterative` models are used for flow simulation under well-mixed ABL conditions, i.e. CBL or NRL. The former serves as a benchmark for evaluating power outputs derived from SCADA data and more advanced models, such as `PropagateUpDownIterative` and the MSC model. Since `PropagateDownwind` neglects both local and global blockage effects as well as meso-scale influences on the flow field, it provides a clean reference for isolating the specific effects studied in this work, namely the influence of meso-scale flow features. This enables a more targeted comparison, where the added value of meso-scale modeling can be clearly identified.

Micro-Scale Model Inputs

Once the main model components are defined, such as the choice of wake deficit model and turbulence model, the micro-scale simulation can be tailored to the specific site under investigation. This requires several key input parameters, which are listed in Table 10. First, the turbine layout must be specified by providing the x and y coordinates of each turbine, along with the turbine type. The turbine type is defined as an array of indices, where each index refers to a turbine with specific characteristics. Optionally, a time index or timestamp can also be included as input. However, in this study, the investigated cases are scattered in time, and no time-dependent input is used. Next, the wind speed w_s and wind direction w_d at hub height must be provided as they define the inflow conditions for the simulation. Lastly, the ambient TI must be specified. This value is computed from the TKE and the wind speed. The turbulence intensity is a critical input for the turbulence model, as it influences both the wake expansion and the resulting effective TI at downstream turbines.

Variable	Description	Use
x	Turbine x-position	Defines layout
y	Turbine y-position	Defines layout
time	Time index or timestamp	For temporal alignment
type	Turbine type index	Links turbines to WTypes
ws	Wind speed hub height	Sets inflow wind speed
wd	Wind direction hub height	Sets inflow wind direction
TI	Turbulence intensity hub height	Affects wake expansion

Table 10: Input parameters used in a PyWake model call.

Micro-Scale Model Outputs

The microscale models generate detailed output fields for each combination of wind turbine, wind direction, wind speed, and input turbulence intensity. Key outputs include the *effective local wind speed* (WS_{eff}) and *effective local turbulence intensity* (TI_{eff}), which represent the inflow conditions at each turbine after accounting for terrain effects, wake interactions, and other flow modifications. The resulting *power output* ($Power$) and *thrust coefficient* (CT) are computed using turbine-specific performance curves.

6.3 Multi-Scale Coupling Model

The multi-scale coupling model applied in this study is a DTU in-house implementation. At the time of writing, the methodology has not yet been formally published; however, it is expected to align closely with the approach introduced by Stipa [5]. The model employs a three-layer structure, similar to the MSC framework, to represent key atmospheric layers, as illustrated in Figure 14. As previously discussed, it enables the simultaneous prediction of microscale effects at the turbine level and mesoscale phenomena at the wind farm scale through an iterative coupling procedure, allowing information exchange between the two scales until convergence is achieved. A more detailed overview of the methodology is provided in the literature review (Section 2.5); this section therefore focuses on the required input parameters and resulting model outputs.

MSC Model Outputs

An overview of the required input parameters is provided in Table 11. Similar to the PyWake models, the multi-scale coupling model requires atmospheric and physical input parameters that define the wind field and stratification conditions across multiple vertical layers. The first three inputs, the wind speed (ws), wind direction (wd), and free-stream turbulence intensity (TI_{∞}), are defined as in standard PyWake usage, since they are also required to initialize the micro-scale simulations in the coupling approach. These quantities define the primary inflow conditions at hub height and form the interface between the meso- and micro-scale models.

Variable	Explanation
ws	Wind speed at 90 m height [m/s]
wd	Wind direction at 90 m height [°]
TI_∞	Free-stream turbulence intensity at hub height, scaled from TKE and ws
H_{ground}	Surface level (start of the first layer) [m]
H_{WindFarm}	Wind farm height (start of the second layer) [m]
H_{ABL}	Top of the ABL (start of the third layer) [m]
τ_0	Shear stress at the surface: $\tau_0 = \rho u_*^2$ [Pa]
τ_{WindFarm}	Shear stress at wind farm height [Pa]
ν_t	Bulk-averaged eddy viscosity for each layer [m ² /s]
U_b, W_d	Bulk-averaged wind speed and wind direction in each layer [m/s], [°]
$\Delta\theta$	Potential temperature jump across the inversion [K]
γ	Lapse rate in the free atmosphere [K/m]
θ_0	Reference potential temperature at the surface [K]
Δh	Inversion layer thickness (i.e., $h_2 - h_0$) [m]
ρ	Density of air [kg/m ³]
u_*	Friction velocity [m/s]
g	Gravitational acceleration (9.81 m/s ²)
φ	Site latitude [°]
f_c	Coriolis parameter: $f_c = 2\Omega \sin(\varphi)$ [1/s]

Table 11: Variables used in the multi-scale model and their physical meaning.

Next, the vertical structure of the atmosphere is defined by the base heights of three layers: the surface level (H_{ground}), the wind farm layer (H_{WindFarm}), and the top of the atmospheric boundary layer (H_{ABL}). These heights represent the start of the first, second, and third layers respectively, and determine the extent over which bulk-averaged variables are calculated.

Momentum transfer between layers is characterized through shear stresses. The surface shear stress (τ_0) and the shear stress at the wind farm layer height (τ_{WindFarm}) are key inputs for capturing near-surface and intra-layer momentum exchange. Vertical mixing within each layer is governed by the eddy viscosity (ν_t), while the large-scale flow background is defined by the bulk-averaged wind speed (U_b) and direction (W_d) for each atmospheric layer. These quantities serve as essential inputs to both the microscale and mesoscale coupling schemes.

To account for thermal stratification and stability, the model requires several thermodynamic inputs: the potential temperature jump across the inversion ($\Delta\theta$), the lapse rate in the free atmosphere (γ), the reference surface potential temperature (θ_0), and the inversion layer thickness (Δh), which defines the vertical distance between the top and base of the inversion.

In addition to atmospheric state variables, several physical constants and geophysical parameters must be specified. These include the gravitational acceleration and the site latitude (φ). The Coriolis parameter is then computed using Equation (52), where Ω is the Earth's angular velocity:

$$f_c = 2\Omega \sin(\varphi) \quad (52)$$

Lastly, the spatial extent of the mesoscale model domain must be chosen carefully. Since the flow is solved in Fourier space, the model assumes that the domain is periodic. This means that if the domain is too small, flow structures leaving the domain at the downstream edge, such as the farm wakes, can artificially reappear at the upstream boundary. These non-physical effects may show up as wake traces near the inlet and can affect the solution if not properly avoided. To prevent this, the domain should be large enough to contain all relevant flow features without interference from the boundary effects.

MSC Model Outputs

The microscale models provide turbine-resolved outputs, as detailed in the previous subsection. These include, as mentioned before, the effective inflow conditions and turbine-specific power and thrust estimates used in the iterative procedure. In the coupled setup, the model additionally outputs corresponding mesoscale fields. The mesoscale model yields spatially distributed flow and quantities across the domain. Key outputs include perturbation pressure (p), wind velocity fields (\mathbf{u}), background flow fields (\mathbf{u}_{bg}), and the vertical displacement of the boundary layer (η). Other fields, such as velocity deficit (`deficit`), background deficit (`deficit_bg`), and flow speedup (`Speedup`) provide insight into mesoscale modification of the wind field. Horizontal momentum fluxes are captured through F_{xy} and F_{fringe} . Finally, scalar parameters like the Froude number (Fr) and Brunt–Väisälä frequency (N) characterize the stratification regime.

7 Simulation Configuration

Before presenting the results, this chapter outlines the simulation setup and key methodological decisions that support the power comparison analysis. It begins with the selection of representative atmospheric cases and the criteria applied to ensure reliable and unbiased data. Next, the configuration of both micro- and mesoscale models is described, including input preparation and coupling strategy. Lastly, the tuning procedure for the wake model is detailed to ensure accurate reproduction of the observed power patterns.

7.1 Case Study Description

The simulation study focuses on the Amrumbank West wind farm, introduced earlier in Section 3, and its interaction with the atmospheric boundary layer under westerly flow conditions. This site is selected for its uniform turbine configuration, structured and dense layout, and comprehensive data availability from SCADA, lidar, and mesoscale model sources. Unlike Nordsee Ost, which includes turbines with two different blade types, and Meerwind Süd/Ost, for which no SCADA data is available, Amrumbank West provides a good basis for model validation.

The analysis is limited to westerly wind conditions, defined as a 20° sector centered at 270° , selected based on the dominant wind directions observed during the measurement period, as was previously shown in the wind rose, see Figure 26. This inflow sector aligns with the farm's west–east orientation, making it ideal for studying wake evolution and meso-scale inflow effects. Under these conditions, the first and twelfth turbine rows act as inflow and outflow boundaries, respectively, as illustrated in Figure 37. Row-based definitions are used later in the analysis to quantify wake losses and flow development across the farm.

This configuration also builds upon previous findings from the GLOBE campaign, which reported upstream flow deceleration and downstream re-acceleration within the farm under similar setups [51].

7.2 Final Case Selection

Section 4 outlined the procedure used to filter cases representing well-mixed ABL conditions suitable for applying the Rampanelli potential temperature profile fitting method. While the initial focus was limited to pure CBL cases, the analysis is extended to include NRL conditions, as these also show well-mixed ABL characteristics comparable to those found under convective regimes.

However, in order to select a final set of cases used in this study, some of the previously applied filtering conditions were slightly relaxed, while additional criteria were introduced. This was done with the aim of selecting a set of cases that is as representative and suitable as possible for studying ABL–wind farm interactions, with a focus on the effect of ABL-height.

Figure 37: Layout of the Amrumbank West wind farm, the site under investigation. Turbine IDs are indicated next to their respective positions. The first and twelfth rows are highlighted, corresponding to the inflow and outflow row of the farm under the prevailing westerly wind direction.

Wind Direction Filter

To isolate westerly inflow conditions, a wind direction sector of 260° to 280° is applied using the `wind_direction_IWES_92m` channel from the met mast. This range aligns with the prevailing wind directions during the measurement period and supports consistent inflow conditions for the case analysis.

Site Curtailment Filter

Full wind farm operation is required, implying that all turbines must be generating power without curtailment. If the site were partially curtailed, the analysis would become considerably more complex, as it would require identifying the curtailed turbines and incorporating this information into the power models. Curtailment can significantly alter the wind field experienced by downstream turbines, and accounting for such effects would necessitate tailoring each case individually, something we aim to avoid in this study.

To ensure full operation, we use the `Site Curt. Power Lim.` channel from the SCADA dataset, which reports the total available capacity of the wind farm. Timestamps with values ≥ 304 MW are considered to represent periods when the entire wind farm is operating without curtailment. The distribution of this channel is shown in Figure 38, where the 304 MW threshold is indicated by a red dashed line in both the histogram and the cumulative distribution function, Figure 38a and Figure 38b, respectively. From the CDF in Figure 38, it can be seen that just before the 304 MW threshold, the cumulative distribution reaches approximately 40%, indicating that around 60% of all timestamps are retained before applying the filtering criteria discussed before and in this section.

(a) Histogram of site curtailment power limit.

(b) CDF of site curtailment power limit.

Figure 38: Distribution of the Site Curt. Power Lim. channel used to assess full wind farm operation. The red dashed line in both plots indicates the 304 MW threshold at which the wind farm is considered fully operational.

Wind Speed Filter

In addition to the site curtailment filtering, we are by definition only interested in the partial load region of the power curve, i.e., the conditions for which the wind speed lies between the cut-in and rated wind speeds. In the *full load region*, the power output reaches its rated value, and the influence of meso-scale flow effects is no longer reflected in the power signal. This is because power models will simply return the rated power for all, or a subset of, turbines, thereby masking any underlying flow variability across the wind farm. Different approaches were explored to know the wind speed in front of the wind farm.

Initially, the met mast wind speed at 92 m was used as input for the analysis. However, plotting the SCADA-based power output of the first-row middle turbine—turbine A37—as a function of this met mast wind speed reveals a large degree of scatter, as shown in Figure 39a. The observed power values deviate significantly from the expected reference power curve for the Senvion 3.6 MW turbine. Using the met mast wind speed directly as input to the power models would introduce considerable complexity in the comparison between modeled power output and SCADA measurements, as the modeled power can deviate substantially from the actual turbine performance. For instance, there are timestamps where a relatively low wind speed of 7.5 m/s corresponds to rated power output, and conversely, cases where higher wind speeds result in significantly lower power values than expected. These inconsistencies would require case-specific adjustments and ultimately undermine the reliability of model-based performance assessments.

To address this issue, the *Farm-Average Wind Spd.* channel from the SCADA data was explored. As mentioned earlier, this channel reports the effective wind speed based on the top 5–10% best-performing turbines. For Amrumbank West, these turbines would ideally be located in the first row, where wake effects are minimal. However, inspection of the corresponding power values revealed that

the most efficient turbines were often not situated in the front row and sometimes appeared randomly distributed across the farm. This undermines the reliability of the farm-averaged wind speed as an approximation for the undisturbed upstream wind. Figure 59b, which shows SCADA power output plotted against this metric, supports this conclusion.

Figure 39: SCADA power output of turbine A37 plotted as a function of (a) met mast wind speed at 92 m and (b) farm-averaged wind speed, defined as the average wind speed of the seven most efficient turbines in the farm.

To obtain a representative wind speed input for the power model, a method was applied in which the average power output of the first turbine row, consisting of turbines A01, A13, A25, A37, A48, A59, and A70, was first computed. Using this row-averaged power, the corresponding wind speed was then estimated by inverting the reference power curve.

It should be noted that this approach is not ideal, as the estimated wind speed inherently includes the effects of local and global blockage. As a result, the actual upstream wind speed is likely somewhat higher than the obtained value. At the time of analysis, it became clear that upstream lidar measurements, available for the western inflow direction, would have been a more accurate alternative. This option was initially eliminated due to the intent to include other wind conditions, like eastern winds, in the broader study, during which the lidar would be located in the wake region and thus unusable. Nonetheless, incorporating upstream lidar data for westerly wind directions could be a valuable extension for future work.

Final Case Selection

For the final case selection, additional filtering criteria are applied. Specifically, the analysis focuses on cases that, in addition to being classified as CBL or NRL regimes, exhibit near-neutral stability within the SL. This ensures that the atmospheric stability is approximately neutral throughout the lowest 250 meters, including the vertical extent over which the PTD is evaluated. By enforcing this condition, the influence of stability on the results is minimized. For completeness, fig:histPBLHall shows the histogram of ABL height for the different stability classes after applying all the above criteria.

For our final case selection, we aim for an ABL-height distribution that is as uniform as possible. However, it is evident that the number of cases is very limited at low ABL heights. To address this, we slightly relax the σ threshold used in the ABL regime classification—specifically, we increase the upper bound of our considered cases from $\text{PTD} < 0.2\text{ K}$ to $\text{PTD} < 0.5\text{ K}$. This can be justified by the following reasoning: since the SL typically represents the lowest $\pm 10\%$ of the ABL, it is possible that the potential temperature at 50 meters used in the PTD calculation is still influenced by surface effects. Figure 40b shows the distribution of the neutral cases, both for $\text{PTD} < 0.2\text{ K}$ and for the additional cases included when relaxing the threshold to 0.5 K . The result is a more balanced distribution of ABL height.

(a) Stacked histogram of ABL height by stability class (SL), after all filters.

(b) Neutral cases: stacked ABL height for $\text{PTD} < 0.2\text{ K}$ and $0.2\text{--}0.5\text{ K}$.

Figure 40: ABL height distributions for final case selection.

To avoid bias from overrepresentation of specific days, the final case selection prioritizes temporal diversity by maximizing the number of unique days per 100 m ABL height bin. Additionally, the number of cases per day is kept as low as possible. Figure 41a presents the resulting ABL height histogram, colored by the number of unique days in each bin. All bins contain at least three unique days, except for the first and last, which include two and one, respectively. Figure 41b shows the temporal distribution of selected cases across the full measurement period, with most days contributing between one and eight timestamps. For completeness, the final ABL height histogram is also shown, stacked by stability category, distinguishing cases with $\text{PTD} < 0.2\text{ K}$ from those between 0.2 and 0.5 K . This highlights that lower ABL heights are generally associated with more stable conditions, an important aspect for the analysis in the next section.

(a) Final ABL height histogram, colored by number of unique days per 100 m bin. (b) Temporal distribution of selected cases and stacked histogram by PTD.

Figure 41: Final case selection distribution, both in ABL-height and in time.

7.3 Model Configuration and Inputs

This subsection specifies the complete set of inputs and parameter values required to initialize and run both the microscale and mesoscale models. For the microscale PyWake models, this includes turbine and site characteristics, as well as flow variables derived from SCADA and meteorological data. For the mesoscale coupling model, the setup involves defining atmospheric layer heights, physical constants, domain dimensions, and numerical parameters.

Micro-Scale Pywake Models

Building on the general PyWake model structure introduced in Table 9, the specific components selected for this study are as follows. Wake losses are modeled using the NiayifarGaussianDeficit, with wake combination handled via LinearSum. Rotor-averaged wind speed is computed using the GaussianOverlapAvgModel, and wake-added turbulence is represented by the CrespoHernandez model. No deflection or ground models are included. In line with the findings of Stipa et al. [5], turbine mirroring is intentionally omitted, as the Niayifar and Porté-Agel (2016) wake model implicitly accounts for enhanced wake recovery within the farm when mirroring is excluded, leading to improved agreement with measured production patterns.

The corresponding input variables used in the model are summarized in Table 10. Specifically, the coordinates and turbine types of all wind turbines in the surrounding cluster are provided. Although the analysis focuses on the Amrumbank West wind farm, the full cluster must be included to realistically capture flow interactions, as the more southern wind farms influence the wind field upstream of Amrumbank West and within. The input wind speed is derived from the method described previously, based on SCADA-estimated wind speeds and power curve inversion. Wind direction is taken from the nearby met mast at 92 m, close to hub height. Turbulence intensity is estimated from WRF-modeled TKE and wind speed using

a modified version of the classical definition $TI = \sigma_u/\bar{u}$, where σ_u is the standard deviation of the longitudinal velocity component. Assuming isotropic turbulence, σ_u is approximated as $\sqrt{2/3 \cdot TKE}$. To improve consistency with observed TI values, typically derived from SCADA or lidar measurements, the wind speed in the denominator is scaled by an empirical factor of 0.8, resulting in the expression shown in Equation (53).

$$TI = \frac{\sqrt{2/3 \cdot TKE}}{WS \cdot 0.8} \quad (53)$$

Multi-Scale Coupling Models

To account for background mesoscale effects in the coupling model, several additional inputs are required, as listed in Table 11. These inputs enable consistent integration of large-scale atmospheric forcing into the multi-layer coupling framework.

Next, the lower height of the different layers is set. Here, H_{ground} is set to 2 m, while H_{WindFarm} is chosen as twice the hub height (i.e., 178 m for the Senvion 3.6 MW turbines). The ABL height H_{ABL} is obtained by fitting the potential temperature profile using the Rampanelli method. This fitting procedure also provides the inversion strength $\Delta\theta$, the free-atmospheric lapse rate γ , the surface reference potential temperature θ_0 , and the inversion layer thickness Δh .

The friction velocity u_* is extracted from the UST channel in the WRF output and is used to compute the surface shear stress τ_0 as in Equation (54), where ρ is the air density, available in the WRF output.

$$\tau_0 = \rho \cdot u_*^2, \quad (54)$$

Assuming a vertically decaying stress profile, the shear stress at any height z is modeled as shown in Equation (55), following the idealized form proposed by Allaerts et al. [44, 48], where the surface shear stress diminishes toward the top of the ABL to reflect reduced momentum flux. The parameter H_{ABL} represents the height of the atmospheric boundary layer, and β is a shape parameter controlling the rate of vertical decay. This formulation allows to calculate the shear stress at the interface between the first and second layer, i.e., the at wind farm height H_{WindFarm} .

$$\tau(z) = \tau_0 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{z}{H_{\text{ABL}}}\right)^\beta, \quad (55)$$

The bulk-averaged wind speed U_b and wind direction W_d for each layer are computed from WRF data blended with ERA5, similar to the approach used for the potential temperature profiles. The layer-wise eddy viscosity ν_t is derived using empirical parameterizations based on inputs adopted from Stipa et al. [5]. While this introduces some uncertainty, we expect the impact of small variations in these inputs on the flow field to be limited.

The gravitational constant is set as $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$, and the site latitude as $\varphi = 54.1^\circ$. This results in a Coriolis parameter of $f_c \approx 1.18 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, computed using the relation $f_c = 2\Omega \sin(\varphi)$ with Earth’s rotation rate $\Omega = 7.2921 \times 10^{-5} \text{ rad/s}$.

To resolve the mesoscale flow dynamics, a horizontal domain of approximately $400 \times 203 \text{ km}^2$ is defined in the streamwise and spanwise directions, respectively. This domain configuration follows the setup used by Stipa et al. [5], who adopted a similar $400 \times 200 \text{ km}^2$ layout to capture large-scale atmospheric interactions with wind farms in the 3LM approach. These large domain dimensions are also necessary to prevent non-physical wrap-around effects caused by the Fourier-space solver, where flow structures exiting the downstream boundary, e.g., the wakes, can artificially reappear at the upstream boundary due to the periodic boundary assumptions. The domain is discretized using a uniform horizontal grid with a resolution of 500 m in both directions. The extended streamwise length allows for full wake development, aligned with the prevailing westerly wind direction considered in this study. The MMI coupling scheme is limited to a maximum of ten iterations with a convergence tolerance of 10^{-4} . In practice, five iterations are typically sufficient to reduce the pressure residual below the threshold, ensuring stable and consistent coupling between mesoscale flow and wake dynamics.

7.4 Wake Model Tuning

Although the selected PyWake submodels were introduced previously, further tuning is required to reflect site-specific wake behavior at Amrumbank West. Differences in layout, turbine configuration, and atmospheric conditions necessitate calibration of the `NiayifarGaussianDeficit` and `CrespoHernandez` models. The tuning aims to align the modeled power drop across the first few downstream rows with SCADA observations, ensuring that both near-wake behavior and the downstream trend are realistically captured.

Generally, the objective is to tune specific parameters in both submodels with the aim of matching the normalized power values of at least the first 2 to 3 downstream rows in the wake-only model with the SCADA data, while ensuring that the overall downstream trend is captured. All power values are normalized by the average power of the first row. Note that this approach removes any differences in first-row power output, since the wake-only model does not account for the potential blockage effect that may influence the performance of the front row in reality.

As a first step, the wake model is tuned to better align with the observed SCADA power data. Section 2.3 introduced the formulation for the wake growth parameter k , see, and linked it dynamically to TI through a linear relationship with constants a_1 and a_2 , representing the slope and baseline of the expansion, respectively. A higher a_1 increases the sensitivity of wake growth to turbulence, while a_2 defines the minimum expansion rate under low-TI conditions [30].

The default constants, based on LES studies by the Porté-Agel group, are $a_1 = 0.3837$ and $a_2 = 0.003678$ [30]. However, in this study, the best agreement between the wake-only model and the normalized SCADA power data was achieved with

the values $a_1 = 0.245$ and $a_2 = 0.004$, respectively. This tuning reflects a reduced sensitivity to turbulence (lower a_1) and a slightly increased baseline wake expansion (higher a_2). Specifically, it suggests that the wakes tend to expand more slowly with increasing turbulence and persist longer downstream due to reduced mixing and slower recovery.

In addition to wake expansion tuning, the parameters of the wake-added turbulence model by Crespo and Hernández are revised to improve agreement with LES results. A detailed comparison of the different turbulence models is not included in the literature review to keep its scope manageable. However, the turbulence model by Crespo and Hernández was originally developed to provide simple and reliable expressions for estimating turbulence characteristics in the wake of single turbines. For the far wake, i.e., for $5 < x/D < 15$, the model given by Equation (56) was proposed.

$$\Delta I_m = 0.73 a^{0.8325} I_x^{-0.0325} \left(\frac{x}{D} \right)^{-0.32} \quad (56)$$

Similar to the approach by Stipa et al., the original coefficients were revisited, with particular focus on the leading constant. This procedure resulted in an optimal value of $d_s = 0.88$, slightly higher than the original value of 0.73, and consistent with the tuning efforts of Stipa. For the other three remaining constants, the original ones reported by Crespo and Hernández were used.

It should be remarked that the empirically obtained parameters above represent one possible tuning configuration, but are not unique. During the tuning process, it was observed that different parameter combinations can yield similarly good agreement with the measurements. A similar conclusion was drawn by Stipa et al. [5].

Figure 42 shows the normalized row-averaged power for both the SCADA data and the `PropagateDownwind` model, which includes only wake effects. Normalization is consistently based on the average power of the first row. Figure 42a presents results for the full dataset, including all turbines and timestamps, while Figure 42b applies a directional filter: SCADA data are included only when the nacelle yaw lies within the predefined wind sector (260° – 280°). Model tuning was applied only for cases with ABL height above 800 m, where mesoscale coupling is expected to be weak. As shown, this tuning results in good agreement between model and data for the first three rows under yaw-filtered conditions.

However, it should be noted that the normalized row-averaged power values show a more irregular trend when using the yaw-direction-filtered dataset, in contrast to the smoother, generally decreasing trend observed without filtering. Figure 43a shows the distribution of nacelle yaw directions for all turbines and all timestamps. It is clear that a substantial portion of the data is excluded by applying the yaw-direction filter: only 43.75% of the original dataset is retained. Additionally, the distributions show a longer tail extending toward lower yaw angles (left of the sector) compared to the right, indicating asymmetry.

(a) Normalized row-averaged power for all studied cases.

(b) Normalized row-averaged power for cases filtered by SCADA-reported nacelle yaw direction (260° – 280°).

Figure 42: Comparison of normalized row-averaged power: (a) using the full dataset, (b) using a yaw-direction-filtered subset.

Furthermore, Figure 43b displays boxplots of the nacelle yaw directions per turbine row, with the green background, the considered sector. One can see that, across nearly the entire wind farm, the row-averaged nacelle yaw directions are consistently lower than expected based on the met mast 92 m wind direction filter previously applied and used as an input of the simulations.

Notably, even the first unawaked row shows a systematic deviation from the expected inflow direction. This could be indicative of a blockage-induced flow deflection in front of the wind farm, a phenomenon also observed by J. Sneeman et al. using lidar measurements.

(a) Histogram of SCADA-reported nacelle yaw directions (all turbines, all time-steps).

(b) Boxplot of nacelle yaw directions per row; the green zone indicates the considered sector.

Figure 43: SCADA-based nacelle yaw statistics used for directional filtering.

8 Results & Discussion

This section presents the key findings of the study, starting with an evaluation of atmospheric stability based on the Froude number and Brunt–Väisälä frequency, two commonly used indicators of stratification and gravity wave activity. Subsequently, model performance is assessed by analyzing the relative error between predicted and SCADA-measured wind farm power. This evaluation begins with an overall comparison across all cases, followed by a breakdown as a function of ABL height to assess sensitivity to ABL depth. To place these trends in a broader theoretical context, results are then interpreted through the lens of the Froude number. Finally, mesoscale model outputs, such as pressure perturbations and ABL displacement, are analyzed to reinforce our findings.

8.1 Atmospheric Stability Characterization

To evaluate the role of atmospheric stability in modulating wind farm performance, and thereby the influence of mesoscale flow effects on power output, the simulated cases are characterized using two key stability metrics: the Froude number (Fr) and the Brunt–Väisälä frequency (N). These indicators quantify the balance between inertial and buoyancy forces and are fundamental to understanding the generation and propagation of gravity waves in the atmosphere.

8.1.1 The Froude Number

Section 2.4.2 introduced the Froude number and its evaluation (Equation (45)), which distinguishes two flow regimes: subcritical ($Fr < 1$) and supercritical ($Fr > 1$). In subcritical conditions, interfacial gravity waves can propagate upstream along the capping inversion and modify the inflow conditions. In supercritical regimes, this upstream propagation is no longer supported at the inversion interface; any upstream influence must instead originate from deeper internal gravity waves aloft. As atmospheric stability increases, such wave activity tends to intensify, enhancing flow modulation both upstream and downstream of the wind farm.

Figure 44a presents the distribution of Froude numbers across the simulated cases. Most values fall within the range $0.3 \leq Fr \leq 1.3$, while a few isolated cases show Froude numbers around $Fr = 1.5$ and $Fr = 2.0$. The red vertical lines in the figure mark thresholds that separate different stability regimes: strong stratification for $Fr < 0.5$, weak stratification for $Fr > 1.5$, and the transition zone around $Fr = 1$, which is associated with critical conditions. These divisions align with the interpretation derived from the work of Smith [46], who investigated the influence of gravity waves on wind farm efficiency, focusing on the regime $0.5 \leq Fr \leq 1.5$, where wave-induced flow modification is most pronounced.

Complementing this, Allaerts [48] identified the range $0.6 \leq Fr \leq 1.2$ as particularly sensitive to gravity-wave-induced blockage, with the strongest feedback effects occurring near the transition point at $Fr \approx 0.9$. This regime is associated with pronounced upstream influence and reduced wind farm performance due to

gravity wave interactions. The Froude numbers obtained in this study largely fall within this interval, which is therefore given particular attention in the subsequent analysis.

Figure 44b shows the ABL height as a function of the Froude number, color-coded by the corresponding PTD, which serves as an indicator of stability within the ABL. A general trend of increasing ABL height with increasing Froude number can be observed. This is consistent with the formulation of the Froude number, where the ABL height H appears in the denominator under a square root; thus, halving H increases Fr by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$. Around the critical value of $Fr = 1$, however, ABL heights are more broadly distributed. Additionally, the PTD values show a general increase with Froude number, suggesting a trend toward stronger stratification in the lowest 250 m of the ABL under higher Fr conditions. However, this trend does not hold uniformly across all simulated cases and should therefore be interpreted with caution.

(a) Histogram of Froude number for the simulated cases.

(b) Scatter plot of ABL height versus Froude number, color-coded by PTD.

Figure 44: Froude number characteristics for all simulated cases: (a) distribution across the dataset; (b) relationship between Froude number, ABL height, and PTD.

8.1.2 Brunt–Väisälä Frequency N

In addition to the Froude number analysis, we also compute the Brunt–Väisälä frequency N , previously introduced in Section 2.1.2, as a measure of the static stability of the free atmosphere. Higher values of N correspond to increased resistance to vertical displacements and indicate more stable stratification.

Figure 45 presents the distribution of Brunt–Väisälä frequencies computed for all simulated cases. The vertical red dashed lines indicate thresholds used to distinguish between weak ($N < 0.01 \text{ s}^{-1}$), moderate ($0.01 \leq N \leq 0.02 \text{ s}^{-1}$), and strong stratification ($N > 0.02 \text{ s}^{-1}$) regimes. These classifications follow conventions found in literature, including the work of Smith [46], who used $N = 0.01 \text{ s}^{-1}$ as a typical reference value in his study [47]. The histogram bars are colored according to the bin-averaged ABL height, revealing a clear inverse relationship: higher N values tend to correspond to lower boundary-layer heights. This trend is expected, as stronger stratification suppresses vertical mixing, leading to reduced

turbulent entrainment and consequently a shallower ABL, consistent with earlier observations discussed in this work.

The obtained values for N align well with climatological observations. A study by G. Grandoni et al. [56] on the climatology of the Brunt–Väisälä frequency over Milan, Italy, reported monthly-averaged values between 0.01 s^{-1} and 0.015 s^{-1} for altitudes ranging from 1500 to 2500 m, with a tendency toward values around 0.01 s^{-1} and reduced annual variability at higher altitudes. This altitude range corresponds to the free atmosphere above the ABL in the present dataset, where the maximum observed ABL height is approximately 1500 m.

Figure 45: Distribution of Brunt–Väisälä frequency N across all simulated cases. Bars are colored by bin-averaged ABL height. Red dashed lines indicate thresholds for weak, moderate, and strong stratification.

8.2 Microscale Model Performance Across Atmospheric Conditions

This subsection presents the performance of the microscale and MSC models in estimating wind turbine power output, using SCADA measurements as reference. The analysis begins with an evaluation of the overall model relative error across all simulated cases. Next, relative errors are examined as a function of ABL height to assess whether shallow boundary layers enhance sensitivity to mesoscale effects. Finally, results are interpreted through the lens of the Froude number, offering a physical framework for understanding flow-blocking phenomena and mesoscale–wind farm interactions.

8.2.1 Overall Power Prediction Accuracy

The relative error in wind farm power production is defined in Equation (57), where $P_{\text{model}}(t)$ denotes the total power predicted by the model for case t , and $P_{\text{SCADA}}(t)$ is the corresponding measured power from SCADA data. The variable t refers to individual simulation cases rather than a continuous time series. It is important to note that, throughout the remainder of the analysis, only turbines with nacelle yaw

directions falling within the defined sector of interest are considered. This filtering ensures consistency in inflow conditions and improves the reliability of the model evaluation. From here on, ϵ_P is used instead of $\epsilon_{P, 260-280^\circ}$.

$$\epsilon_{P, 260-280^\circ} [\%] = \frac{P_{\text{model}}(t) - P_{\text{SCADA}}(t)}{P_{\text{SCADA}}(t)} \cdot 100 \quad (57)$$

Figure 46 presents the relative error in predicted wind farm power output, ϵ_P , for the different models. The figure includes both the case-wise error values (Figure 46a) and the distribution of those errors across all cases (Figure 46b). The relative error is computed at the wind farm level, i.e., aggregated across all turbines. Cases involving extreme outliers—specifically turbines with errors exceeding 100%—are excluded from the analysis. This filtering step is necessary to remove turbines identified as malfunctioning or significantly underperforming compared to neighboring units under similar inflow conditions. For clarity, the PropagateDownwind model is referred to as 'Wake', the PropagateUpDownIterative model as 'Wake+PUD', and the multi-scale coupling model as 'MSC' throughout the remainder of this section.

(a) Relative error in wind farm power prediction for each case.

(b) Distribution of relative power prediction errors across all cases.

Figure 46: Comparison of relative power prediction error ϵ_P between models at the wind farm level.

Figure 46a highlights a clear reduction in error as additional physical effects are incorporated. The wake-only model, which accounts solely for downstream interactions, exhibits the largest overestimation. Incorporating local blockage effects via the Wake+PUD model reduces this bias by capturing upstream flow deceleration. The most accurate predictions are obtained with the MSC model, which also accounts for mesoscale influences such as background pressure gradients, upstream deceleration, and downstream acceleration within the wind farm. This progression demonstrates how the combined inclusion of local and mesoscale effects enhances the accuracy of power estimation.

Although the mean relative errors appear small, these values should be interpreted with caution. As shown in Figure 46b, the case-wise errors span a wide range, from approximately -60% to $+60\%$, and the distributions are nearly symmetric around zero, as indicated by the dashed vertical line. The green background shading represents the range of $\pm 1\sigma$ around the mean of the KDE. This symmetry accounts for the low average errors observed in Figure 46a, despite the substantial variability across individual cases.

Furthermore, Figure 47 illustrates the distribution of ϵ_P across the turbine rows. Dots indicate the mean relative error, while bars represent the standard deviation. Up to row 5, the MSC model consistently outperforms the microscale models by reducing the relative error. From row 7 onward, however, the MSC model shows higher errors compared to the microscale models. This pattern—improved performance at the front but reduced accuracy toward the end, reflects a spatial variation in model behavior. Such intra-farm differences help explain the overall balance observed in the wind farm-level error statistics. A more detailed interpretation of these trends is provided in the row-averaged normalized power analysis and row-averaged power estimate differences later in this section.

Figure 47: Relative power error ϵ_P per turbine row for all models. Dots indicate mean errors; bars represent standard deviation across cases.

The modest differences in model performance observed here contrast with findings from Stipa et al. [5], where MSC models showed much larger improvements over wake-only models when benchmarked against LES. In this study, SCADA data serve as the reference, which introduces additional uncertainty due to measurement noise, operational variability etc. Furthermore, the low average errors may partly result from spatial averaging, where over- and underestimations across turbines offset one another, a possibility supported by the symmetric KDE distributions and row-wise error trends, and examined further in later sections.

8.2.2 Impact of ABL Height on Power Prediction

Next, the influence of ABL height on model performance is examined. Figure 48 presents the relative wind farm power error, ϵ_P , as a function of ABL height for both the microscale models and the MSC model. ABL height is discretized into 100-meter bins. For each bin, vertical lines indicate the interquartile range (25th–75th percentile), and the background histogram illustrates the distribution of ABL heights across all cases.

Overall, model predictions are largely similar across most ABL heights. However, between 800–1000 m, the MSC model predicts higher power output, reducing the underestimation observed in the microscale models and thus lowering the relative error compared to SCADA data. Below 700 m, the discrepancy between models increases with decreasing ABL height. In this regime, the MSC model consistently reduces the overestimation trend of the microscale models. It is important to note that the final bin includes only a single case and lacks percentile bounds; its associated error value should therefore be interpreted with caution. Additionally, it can be observed that the interquartile range is generally lower for more shallow ABL heights, with spreads around 20% for lower ABL heights and up to a maximum of 40% for high ABL heights. These relatively large interquartile ranges reflect the variability of model results across different atmospheric conditions.

Figure 48: Relative power error versus ABL height, binned per 100 m. Vertical bars show the 25th–75th percentile range; the background histogram indicates ABL height distribution.

Figure 49: Relative wind farm power error for all models, grouped by ABL height regime: all cases, high ABL, and low ABL.

Consistent with the wake model tuning approach, where tuning was performed using cases with ABL heights exceeding 800 m, the dataset is here also split into low- and high-ABL regimes. As indicated by the vertical line in Figure 48, this threshold allows comparison of model errors under different atmospheric mixing conditions.

Figure 49 shows the relative error in wind farm power prediction across all studied cases, grouped by ABL height regime: all cases combined (as in Figure 46a), high ABL height, and low ABL height. As previously noted, when aggregating across all cases, the MSC model yields the most accurate estimates, with an average overprediction of only 1.7%. However, this overall performance masks contrasting behavior across ABL regimes. Under high ABL conditions, the MSC model performs slightly worse than the microscale models. In contrast, under low ABL conditions, it significantly outperforms them by reducing the relative overestimation.

Although the MSC model reaches an average error exactly 0% in the low-ABL regime, this result is more an unfortunate consequence of case grouping than a meaningful indication of perfect accuracy. To illustrate this, the probability density functions of the wind farm power relative error, ϵ_P , are examined separately for the high- and low-ABL regimes, as shown in Figure 50. The spread ranges from approximately -60% to $+60\%$ in the high-ABL regime, and from -40% to $+40\%$ in the low-ABL regime. The distributions are nearly symmetric around zero, as indicated by the dashed line, which explains the small overall mean errors despite significant case-wise variability.

Despite the symmetry observed in the error distributions, the MSC model shows a noticeably sharper peak centered around zero in the low-ABL regime, indicating improved consistency and reduced bias in power predictions compared to the microscale models. This suggests that incorporating mesoscale effects yields benefits under stable, shallow boundary layer conditions. Again, while average relative

errors may seem small, they are the result of aggregating cases with varying atmospheric states and should therefore be interpreted with caution, as compensating over- and underestimations may obscure underlying performance differences.

Figure 50: Probability density functions of the relative wind farm power error, ϵ_P , conditioned on ABL regimes for all models

To evaluate inter-farm differences in model predictions, Figure 51 presents the normalized row-averaged power values for each model, separated by ABL regime. Normalization is performed with respect to the first-row mean power of the Wake model. In the low-ABL regime, the MSC model is the only one closely following the SCADA trend, predicting significantly lower power in the first seven rows compared to the microscale models. Around row 7, MSC predictions exceed those of the microscale models, indicating downstream flow recovery. A similar upward trend is visible in the SCADA data, albeit with a slight delay, resulting in good agreement between MSC and SCADA at the farm's end. In contrast, under high-ABL conditions, all models systematically overpredict power, and the normalized values exhibit a smoother, generally decreasing trend downstream. This spatial behavior looks similar to findings from the GLOBE campaign, where global blockage effects were attributed to an upstream unfavorable pressure gradient reducing front-row power, followed by a favorable gradient within the farm that accelerated the flow and supported faster wake recovery toward the wind farm's outlet.

Figure 51: Normalized power values as a function of the turbine row for the different models under high and low ABL regimes

8.2.3 Model Performance in Relation to Froude Number

The previous analysis focused on presenting the observed trends in model error across ABL regimes without explicitly linking them to the underlying physical mechanisms. This subsection aims to bridge that gap by interpreting the results from the Froude number point of view, which serves as a more standardized metric for assessing the likelihood of ABL–wind farm coupling and the presence of mesoscale phenomena such as flow blocking. As shown in Section 8.1.1, the Froude number in the data set predominantly falls within the range of 0.5 to 1.5, with a decreasing frequency towards higher values. Note that the Fr number is evaluated for interfacial gravity waves according to Equation (45). The following analysis explores how model prediction errors vary across this Froude number range, with the goal of identifying potential performance dependencies on mesoscale flow regimes.

Model Error as a Function of Froude Number

Figure 52 presents the relative error in estimated wind farm power as a function of the Froude number, binned in intervals of 0.1 for all three models. Up to $Fr \approx 0.9$, the models produce similar predictions, with only minor differences. As the Froude number enters the low supercritical range ($Fr \approx 1.1–1.2$), these differences begin to manifest more clearly, particularly with the MSC model showing increased deviations. However, it should be noted that the final two bins contain only two cases each, introducing increased uncertainty, and should therefore be interpreted with caution.

Figure 52: Relative error in estimated wind farm power as a function of Froude number, binned in intervals of 0.1 for all three models.

The above results are somewhat unexpected, as larger differences in model performance were anticipated under subcritical conditions ($Fr < 1$), where interfacial gravity waves can propagate upstream along the inversion layer due to reduced advection speed, enabling stronger vertical flow adjustment. However, as shown by Allaerts and Meyer [48] and also emphasized by Smith [47], significant flow deceleration upstream of wind farms can occur across all regimes, including supercritical conditions. In these cases, interfacial gravity waves are unable to propagate upstream, and any upstream influence must instead originate from internal gravity waves or broader mesoscale pressure field interactions. As mentioned in the previous subsection, the strongest gravity-wave-induced power losses have been observed between $Fr \approx 0.6$ and $Fr \approx 1.2$, indicating that mesoscale effects can remain relevant even when upstream propagation is limited.

Furthermore, D. Allaerts and J. Meyer [48] observed that under low ABL heights and stronger inversion strengths, the peak excitation of these interfacial gravity waves tends to shift upward, toward $Fr \approx 1.0$. In the present results, however, significant model deviations are also observed beyond $Fr = 1.0$, suggesting that Froude number alone may not fully capture the onset of mesoscale influences. This observation points to a possible interaction with ABL height. Referring back to the insights from the previous subsection, where larger deviations were found under low-ABL regimes, it is hypothesized that ABL height modulates the effectiveness of mesoscale coupling, both in sub- and supercritical regime. To explore this further, the dataset is now split into low- and high-ABL regimes to assess how model errors evolve across the Froude number spectrum within each group.

Figure 53 presents the same analysis as Figure 52, but separately for high and low ABL regimes. Remarkably, for high-ABL conditions, the influence of mesoscale effects appears limited, with all models performing similarly across the Froude number range. In contrast, under low-ABL conditions, small but systematic differences between models become more apparent, particularly in the supercritical to near-critical Froude number range.

Figure 53: Relative model error as a function of Froude number, shown separately for high and low ABL regimes.

Intra-Farm Variation in Power Prediction Error

As discussed earlier, strong ABL–wind farm interaction is marked by an upstream unfavorable pressure gradient that lowers front-row power through enhanced blockage, followed by a favorable gradient that accelerates the flow downstream. This characteristic pattern, also observed during the GLOBE campaign [51], is a hallmark of global blockage. To assess whether similar spatial behavior is present here, the analysis is further split up by turbine row position within the wind farm.

Figure 54 shows normalized power as a function of turbine row. Normalization is performed relative to the average power of the first-row turbines in the wake-only model. Under favorable Froude conditions, a clear global blockage is seen with reduced power at the front and increasing power downstream. The MSC model captures this trend more accurately, matching the front-row reduction up to row 3 and outperforming the wake-only model and showing a clear flow acceleration towards the end. In contrast, this spatial pattern is less pronounced outside the favorable Froude number range, where both blockage and downstream acceleration effects are weaker. This is reflected in the MSC model’s more modest reduction in front-row power and a generally uniform or declining power trend downstream. A similar behavior was previously observed in the normalized power profiles for low and high ABL regimes, as shown in Figure 51, suggesting a potential relationship between ABL regime and Froude number regime.

Figure 54: Row-wise normalized power profiles split by Froude number regime, highlighting spatial trends in blockage and downstream recovery.

Building on the above insights, Figure 55 extends the analysis by grouping results according to turbine position within the farm, i.e., the first four rows (front), the middle four rows, and the last four rows (back), to assess how model performance varies along the streamwise direction in relation to both Fr and ABL regime.

Figure 55 shows that even under high-ABL conditions, a characteristic global blockage pattern, upstream deceleration followed by downstream acceleration, is present, albeit less pronounced. In the left panel, the MSC model reduces the overestimation of ϵ_P in the front rows but slightly overestimates the power recovery in the rear rows due to the favorable pressure gradient. Under low-ABL conditions, these effects become more pronounced, with a clearer power deficit in the front rows and increased normalized power downstream. The largest deviations in model performance occur within the Froude number range of approximately 0.8-1.2 for the front rows and 0.6-1.0 for the rear rows, consistent with the range highlighted by Allaerts and Meyer [48] as most sensitive to interfacial gravity-wave-induced effects.

The above analysis highlights significant differences in power prediction across atmospheric conditions, both in terms of ABL height and Froude number. To quantify these differences, Figure 56 presents the relative power deviation between the MSC model and the microscale wake-only model as a function of Froude number, for both high and low ABL regimes. The results are color-coded by turbine row, and the metric shown represents the relative difference between the two model predictions, normalized by the reference SCADA power: $(P_{MSC} - P_{WakeOnly})/P_{SCADA}$.

In general, the spread in model differences is significantly larger under low-ABL conditions than under high-ABL regimes. For high-ABL cases, the differences remain relatively uniform across the Froude number range, with a slight peak around $Fr \approx 0.85$. In this regime, the MSC model tends to estimate the front-row power to be approximately -5% lower relative to the wake-only model, while slightly higher power estimates, up to $+5\%$, are observed toward the wind farm's end. In

Figure 55: Relative power error ϵ_P versus Froude number, split by turbine row and ABL regime.

contrast, under low-ABL conditions, the vertical spread in relative power estimation difference becomes more significant. The MSC model estimates front-row power values around -10% lower, with more pronounced overestimation toward the wind farm's outlet-up to $+10\%$ around $Fr \approx 0.6$. This indicates a steeper gradient in predicted power along the farm layout and highlights the intra-farm variability in power prediction, reflecting the enhanced sensitivity of flow dynamics to mesoscale effects under shallow ABL conditions. Remarkably, big differences are also observed for supercritical conditions.

Figure 56: Relative power difference between the MSC and wake-only model (with respect to SCADA power) as a function of Froude number, shown for high and low ABL regimes and color-coded by turbine row.

Figure 57 further illustrates the sensitivity of ABL height in modulating the strength of mesoscale coupling effects on wind farm power prediction. The figure shows the difference in estimated power relative to SCADA measurements for the first turbine row, with points color-coded by ABL height. Focusing on the relevant Froude number range ($0.6 \leq Fr \leq 1.2$), a clear trend emerges: model differences increase significantly with decreasing ABL height, indicating stronger deviations in shallow boundary layers. While differences persist above the critical Froude number of 1, they are notably smaller. Although this trend is only partially distinct, it could be attributed to the fact that interfacial gravity waves can influence the upstream flow field only under subcritical conditions.

Figure 57: Impact of ABL height on the difference between model-predicted and SCADA power for the first turbine row. Results are shown for both MSC and wake-only models, color-coded by ABL height.

8.3 The Role of ABL Height in Modulating Mesoscale–Wind Farm Interactions

While the previous analyses focused on microscale model outputs, i.e., turbine-level power predictions, the MSC framework resolves both microscale and mesoscale dynamics through its iterative coupling approach. This enables the model not only

to estimate power but also to capture background flow responses to the wind farm, such as changes in wind speed, pressure gradients, and flow structure. Examining these mesoscale outputs provides additional insight into how ABL height but also ABL stability, related with PTD, may influence the strength and spatial extent of mesoscale–wind farm interactions, thereby reinforcing and extending the findings from the power-based evaluation.

Figure 58 shows the pressure perturbation field for a representative timestamp in which the effects of global blockage are clearly visible. This case corresponds to a Froude number of 0.555, an ABL height of approximately 835 m, and a capping inversion strength of 7.46 K. The left panel displays the pressure perturbation field across the broader wind farm region, while the right panel provides a zoomed-in view of the N4 cluster. Note that the computational domain extends beyond the area shown in these plots.

From this zoom-in, a characteristic global blockage feature is clearly visible: elevated pressure upstream of the wind farm and reduced pressure within and downstream of the cluster. This pressure gradient drives flow deceleration in the front rows and acceleration in the rear rows, with a clear sign change around row 7, consistent with the spatial trends observed in the previously presented normalized power plots.

(a) Pressure perturbation field near the wind farm (partial domain view).

(b) Zoom-in on the N4 cluster showing upstream–downstream pressure gradient.

Figure 58: Pressure perturbation field for a global blockage case ($Fr = 0.555$, ABL height = 835 m).

The mesoscale-induced pressure field modifications described above directly influence the wind field encountered by the wind farm. As shown in Equation (58), there is a direct relationship between the pressure perturbation and the displacement of the ABL top, η_t , where ρ_0 and g' represent the air density and reduced gravity, respectively, as defined in Equation (46). An increase in pressure upstream corresponds to a local lifting of the ABL, which, under mass conservation, leads to a reduction in horizontal wind speed within the affected layer. This upstream deceleration is a key signature of global blockage. Figure 59a illustrates the spatial pattern of ABL displacement η , while Figure 59b shows the associated flow deficit resulting from this mesoscale adjustment. The blue zone upstream reflects the presence of global blockage.

$$\frac{p_1}{\rho_0} = g' \eta_t \quad (58)$$

(a) ABL displacement η due to upstream pressure buildup. (b) Flow deficit pattern corresponding to mesoscale-induced pressure field.

Figure 59: Mesoscale pressure–ABL interactions and impact on flow structure.

As the upstream pressure buildup serves as a potential indicator of global blockage intensity, it Figure 60a presents the maximum mesoscale-induced pressure perturbation near the Amrumbank West wind farm. Within the Froude number range $0.6 \leq Fr \leq 1.2$, a trend seems to emerge: pressure buildup tends to increase as the ABL height decreases. This observation may suggest that shallower boundary layers are associated with stronger flow resistance and more pronounced mesoscale–wind farm interactions, likely driven by interfacial gravity wave dynamics.

However, this relationship is not entirely straightforward. While higher perturbation pressures are generally observed at lower ABL heights, they also tend to increase with Froude number, which can be partially explained by the inverse dependence of Fr on ABL height. Yet, certain cases within this Fr range exhibit elevated PTD values, indicating a shift in ABL regime. Star-shaped markers in Figure 60a highlight cases where the PTD exceeds $0.2 K$ —the threshold proposed by Liu et al. [11] for distinguishing well-mixed boundary layers from more stable ABL-regimes. Focusing on the supercritical flow regime, it can be observed that certain cases still exhibit high maximum pressure perturbations. However, these coincide with a greater number of scatter points showing a PTD above $0.2 K$, suggesting a more stable ABL. In such conditions, vertical mixing is suppressed, and the development of internal gravity waves may contribute to the overall pressure gradient. This aligns with the findings of Allaerts [48], who noted that “at very high Froude numbers, internal gravity waves dominate interfacial waves, and the perturbation levels increase instead of decrease with ABL stratification”.

To elaborate a bit further on this Figure 60b shows ABL height as a function of PTD, color-coded by the maximum pressure perturbation. Up to the $0.2 K$ threshold, the previously observed trend, namely, increasing pressure perturbation with decreasing ABL height, holds consistently. This is expected given the near-neutral character of the ABL, where the influence of internal gravity waves is likely limited. Beyond this threshold, however, the relationship becomes more scattered,

suggesting a shift toward greater uncertainty. In this regime, the relative contribution of internal gravity waves to the total pressure build-up may increase, while the influence of interfacial waves will depend on the corresponding Fr number, i.e., subcritical or supercritical.

A general trend can be identified whereby higher maximum pressure perturbations are typically associated with lower ABL heights. This trend often coincides with elevated Froude numbers, which can be partially explained by the inverse relationship between Fr and ABL height in its definition. The relationship appears to hold particularly well under near-neutral to weakly stable conditions, i.e., for PTD values below 0.2 K. At higher Froude numbers, frequently linked to more stable ABLs, PTD values also tend to increase. This behaviour suggests that enhanced internal gravity wave activity may contribute to additional pressure build-up under such conditions. Further investigation is required to disentangle the respective roles of interfacial and internal gravity waves in shaping the observed pressure perturbations, and to clarify how their influence varies across different flow regimes.

(a) Maximum pressure perturbation [Pa] in the mesoscale domain around the studied wind farm.

(b) Same as (a), now highlighting the role of atmospheric stability via PTD values.

Figure 60: Mesoscale pressure buildup as a function of Froude number, ABL height, and atmospheric stability. Low ABL heights and strong stratification promote stronger upstream pressure signals.

9 Conclusion

This thesis validated DTU's in-house MSC model, developed for efficient prediction of wind farm–atmosphere interactions under varying atmospheric conditions. Using SCADA and meteorological data, its ability to simulate flow dynamics and power performance was evaluated under well-mixed boundary layers, and benchmarked against standard micro-scale wake models in PyWake.

The study focused on the Amrumbank West wind farm in the N4 cluster, chosen for its uniform turbine layout and rich, high-resolution dataset—including SCADA, lidar, met mast observations, and mesoscale outputs from the GLOBE campaign. Among neighboring farms, it offers the most consistent setup for model validation, as Nordsee Ost includes mixed rotor types and Meerwind Süd/Ost lacks SCADA data.

To isolate the effect of atmospheric stability on wind farm efficiency and examine flow regimes from subcritical to supercritical, the study focused on conventionally neutral (C(N)BL) conditions using a targeted filtering approach. A primary filter applied a potential temperature difference threshold of 0.2 K between 50 and 250 m to exclude stable cases, slightly relaxed to 0.5 K to better capture shallow ABLs and ensure a more uniform ABL-height distribution. Additional filters included wind direction ($270^\circ \pm 20^\circ$), sub-rated wind speeds, and exclusion of curtailed turbines. Final timestamps were manually selected to ensure coverage across different days and meteorological conditions, with emphasis on achieving a broad and uniform distribution in ABL height.

Input wind speed to the models was estimated using a reverse power curve approach based on the mean power of the first turbine row, thereby avoiding reliance on SCADA-reported effective wind speeds, which are often distorted by inflow effects. To improve alignment between model assumptions and measurements, a yaw filter was applied, retaining only turbines with nacelle orientations between 260° and 280° , which reduced discrepancies with mast-reported wind directions. Wake tuning was limited to cases with ABL heights above 800 m, where meso-scale flow reorganization is expected to play a minor role due to well-mixed conditions.

The MSC model employs a three-layer ABL representation and iteratively couples micro- and meso-scale effects. Background stratification was characterized using the Rampanelli potential temperature profile fit, providing key parameters to define inflow and link mesoscale forcing to turbine-scale wake dynamics. MSC was benchmarked against two PyWake reference models: `PropagateDownwind`, which includes only downstream wake effects, and `PropagateUpDownwindIterative`, which also accounts for local blockage.

Although farm-level power errors may appear small, they show substantial variability across individual cases and spatial positions. Global averages often balance over- and underestimations, masking systematic differences. To uncover

these, model performance was analyzed as a function of ABL height. A clear trend emerges: as ABL height decreases, deviations between MSC and microscale models increase, indicating stronger coupling with the background atmosphere. Row-averaged normalized power profiles reinforce this, with blockage features, i.e. reduced front-row power and downstream recovery, becoming more pronounced in shallow ABLs. The MSC model captures this spatial pattern more accurately.

To interpret ABL-dependent model behavior from a dynamical perspective, results are further examined in terms of the Froude number. While this parameter distinguishes subcritical ($Fr < 1$) from supercritical ($Fr > 1$) flow regimes and indicates the potential for upstream-propagating interfacial gravity waves, the observed model differences across the relevant range ($0.6 \leq Fr \leq 1.2$) were different than anticipated. Deviations were not limited to subcritical conditions; significant differences were also present in supercritical cases. When grouped by ABL height and turbine row, deviations persisted across the Froude spectrum but remained limited in high-ABL scenarios. In contrast, low-ABL conditions exhibited more pronounced intra-farm variability, with the MSC model predicting up to 10% lower front-row power, consistent with stronger upstream deceleration under enhanced global blockage.

Linking model behavior to mesoscale outputs reveals that maximum upstream pressure perturbation generally increases near the critical $Fr = 1$ threshold as ABL height decreases. Interestingly, for certain supercritical cases, pressure perturbations continue to rise, likely suggesting a growing influence of internal gravity waves, particularly under stronger stratification. Cross-referencing with PTD, used as a proxy for ABL stability, indicates that the inverse relationship between ABL height and pressure perturbation holds predominantly for PTD values below 0.2 K. Beyond this threshold, corresponding to more stable conditions, the correlation weakens and pressure variability increases.

Overall, these findings underscore that pressure build-up is closely linked to ABL height within the examined Froude number range. In supercritical regimes, the pressure perturbation appears to be increasingly influenced by internal gravity waves. However, given the limited number of supercritical cases, further investigation is required to better resolve the governing dynamics in this regime. In particular, the role of ABL stability—and specifically the contribution of internal gravity waves to the total pressure build-up under more stratified conditions—requires further investigation.

10 Limitations & Future Work

This section summarizes the main limitations of the study and outlines directions for future research.

Despite access to a comprehensive GLOBE dataset (SCADA, lidar, met mast, mesoscale model outputs), the final case set was reduced substantially by strict filtering based on wind direction, turbine status, ABL regime, and inflow consistency. This reflects a common challenge in wind energy research: even rich datasets can fall short under tight atmospheric and operational constraints.

The analysis was limited to well-mixed C(N)BL regimes, selected to align with assumptions embedded in the current MSC framework. While this improves internal model consistency, it limits generalizability. Future work could extend the analysis to weakly stable or convective ABLs, though this would require major updates to the MSC submodels, e.g., wake expansion, velocity profiles, and turbulence intensity, which currently assume neutral stratification. Stability-aware modeling is essential, as stratified flows suppress turbulence and alter wake dynamics.

Inflow wind speed was estimated using a reverse power curve based on front-row turbine output, with wind direction taken from the met mast at Nordsee Ost's southern edge. Yaw differences led to additional data filtering. The analysis focused on westerly inflow, given its frequency and alignment with farm orientation. Future work could investigate other sectors (e.g., northerly or easterly), where terrain and effective farm length may alter coupling behavior. Lidar data at Amrumbank West and targeted campaigns or synthetic datasets could support such efforts. Additionally, due to the lack of direct eddy viscosity and surface stress data, parametric mixing estimates and LES results were used.

Stability was hard to define due to large differences in height-specific metrics like Obukhov length. To avoid this, PTD between 50 and 250 m was used as a bulk measure of stratification. While more consistent, PTD still showed some variation with height. The Rampanelli fit worked well for most cases but had issues with weakly stable profiles. Stipa et al. [5] suggested an improved version with an extra basis function to handle such cases, which could help increase the number of usable timestamps.

With a larger dataset after filtering, it would be possible to better explore the supercritical regime, where a current data gap limits investigation into the behavior of internal and interfacial gravity waves under typically more stratified conditions within this Fr range.

Despite the above limitations, the MSC model provides a robust foundation for exploring wind farm–atmosphere interactions and offers a valuable framework for future research on this topic.

References

- [1] Jørgensen, Birte Holst and Remler, Karina. *IEA Wind TCP Denmark 2022*. Reviewed by: Christoph Wolter, Danish Energy Agency; Christian Sjøstrann Jørgensen, Danish Energy Agency. Technical University of Denmark (DTU) and Danish Energy Agency, 2022. URL: <https://ens.dk/service/statistik-data-noegletal-og-kort/maanedlig-og-aarlig-energistatistik>.
- [2] International Energy Agency (IEA). *World Energy Outlook 2023*. Licence: CC BY 4.0 (report); CC BY NC SA 4.0 (Annex A). Paris: International Energy Agency, 2023. URL: <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2023>.
- [3] Grid, National. *The North Sea: A future clean energy powerhouse*. 2025. URL: <https://www.nationalgrid.com/stories/energy-explained/north-sea-future-clean-energy-powerhouse>.
- [4] Guardian, The. *Denmark: Showing the world what is possible with North Sea green power*. 2025. URL: <https://www.theguardian.com/delivering-the-energy-transition/2025/feb/04/denmark-showing-world-possible-north-sea-green-power-plant-europe>.
- [5] Stipa, Sebastiano et al. “The multi-scale coupled model: a new framework capturing wind farm–atmosphere interaction and global blockage effects”. In: *Wind energy science* 9.5 (May 2024), pp. 1123–1152. DOI: 10.5194/wes-9-1123-2024. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-9-1123-2024>.
- [6] Sempreviva, Anna Maria et al. “Wind modelling and simulation at mesoscale and microscale for wind energy applications”. In: *Proceedings of the European Wind Energy Conference and Exhibition (EWEA)*. 2019. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336423663_Wind_modelling_and_simulation_at_mesoscale_and_microscale_for_wind_energy_applications.
- [7] Universitet, Danmarks Tekniske. *Studiehåndbog 98/99 : elektro*. Danmarks Tekniske Universitet, 1998. ISBN: 9788787335607.
- [8] Peña, Alfredo, Gryning, Sven-Erik, and Hasager, Charlotte B. “Measurements and modelling of the wind speed profile in the marine atmospheric boundary layer”. In: *Boundary-Layer Meteorology* 129.3 (Oct. 2008), pp. 479–495. DOI: 10.1007/s10546-008-9323-9. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10546-008-9323-9>.
- [9] Hatfield, Daniel, Gottschall, Julia, and Hasager, Charlotte Bay. “Stability information derived from a floating lidar system using bulk Richardson formulation”. In: *Journal of Physics Conference Series* 2265.4 (May 2022), p. 042024. DOI: 10.1088/1742-6596/2265/4/042024. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2265/4/042024>.
- [10] Stull, Roland B. *An introduction to boundary layer meteorology*. Jan. 1988. DOI: 10.1007/978-94-009-3027-8. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-3027-8>.

- [11] Liu, Shuyan and Liang, Xin-Zhong. “Observed diurnal cycle climatology of planetary boundary layer height”. In: *Journal of Climate* 23.21 (June 2010), pp. 5790–5809. DOI: 10.1175/2010jcli3552.1. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1175/2010jcli3552.1>.
- [12] Che, Junhui and Zhao, Ping. “Characteristics of the summer atmospheric boundary layer height over the Tibetan Plateau and influential factors”. In: *Atmospheric chemistry and physics* 21.7 (Apr. 2021), pp. 5253–5268. DOI: 10.5194/acp-21-5253-2021. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-21-5253-2021>.
- [13] Liu, Shuyan and Liang, Xin-Zhong. “Diagnosing the Convective Boundary Layer with the Potential Temperature Difference Method”. In: *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences* 80.2 (2023), pp. 341–361. DOI: 10.1175/JAS-D-22-0159.1.
- [14] Tennekes, H. “A model for the dynamics of the inversion above a convective boundary layer”. In: *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences* 30.4 (1973), pp. 558–567. DOI: 10.1175/1520-0469(1973)030<0558:AMFTD0>2.0.CO;2.
- [15] Betts, Alan K. “Non-precipitating cumulus convection and its parameterization”. In: *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society* 99.419 (1973), pp. 178–196. DOI: 10.1002/qj.49709941915.
- [16] Deardorff, J. W. “Prediction of convective mixed-layer entrainment zones in different instability regimes”. In: *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences* 36.3 (1979), pp. 424–436. DOI: 10.1175/1520-0469(1979)036<0424:POCMLE>2.0.CO;2.
- [17] Fitzjarrald, David R. and Garstang, Michael. “Vertical Structure of the Convective Boundary Layer: Some Observations and Interpretations”. In: *Journal of Climate and Applied Meteorology* 20.12 (1981), pp. 1332–1344. DOI: 10.1175/1520-0450(1981)020<1332:VSOTCB>2.0.CO;2.
- [18] Steyn, D. G., Baldi, M., and Hoff, R. M. “The Detection of Mixed Layer Depth and Entrainment Zone Thickness from Lidar Backscatter Profiles”. In: *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology* 16.7 (1999), pp. 953–959. DOI: 10.1175/1520-0426(1999)016<0953:TDOMLD>2.0.CO;2.
- [19] Rampanelli, G. and Zardi, D. “A method to determine the capping inversion layer in the convective boundary layer using radiosonde data”. In: *Journal of Applied Meteorology* 43.6 (2004), pp. 927–940. DOI: 10.1175/1520-0450(2004)043<0927:AMTDIT>2.0.CO;2.
- [20] School, Utrecht Summer. *Encroachment and Entrainment in the Convective Boundary Layer*. Lecture notes, Physics of the Climate System, Utrecht Summer School. 2023. URL: <https://www.utrechtsummerschool.nl/>.
- [21] Jensen, N. O. *A Note on Wind Generator Interaction*. Tech. rep. Risø-M No. 2411. Roskilde, Denmark: Risø National Laboratory, 1983. URL: <https://orbit.dtu.dk/en/publications/2ac0aed9-af5e-4a3e-94f0-6ca825631180>.

- [22] Bastankhah, Majid and Porté-Agel, Fernando. “A new analytical model for wind-turbine wakes”. In: *Renewable Energy* 70 (June 2014), pp. 116–123. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2014.01.002. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2014.01.002>.
- [23] Frandsen, Sten et al. “Analytical modelling of wind speed deficit in large offshore wind farms”. In: *Wind Energy* 9.1-2 (Jan. 2006), pp. 39–53. DOI: 10.1002/we.189. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.189>.
- [24] Katić, I., Højstrup, J., and Jensen, N. O. “A Simple Model for Cluster Efficiency”. In: *European Wind Energy Association Conference and Exhibition (EWEC '86)*. Rome, Italy: A. Raguzzi, 1987, pp. 407–410.
- [25] Tennekes, H. and Lumley, J. L. *A First Course in Turbulence*. The MIT Press, 1972.
- [26] Johansson, P., George, W., and Gourlay, M. “Equilibrium similarity, effects of initial conditions and local Reynolds number on the axisymmetric wake”. In: *Physics of Fluids* 15.3 (2003), pp. 603–617.
- [27] Dufresne, N. and Wosnik, M. “Velocity deficit and swirl in the turbulent wake of a wind turbine”. In: *Marine Technology Society Journal* 47.4 (2013), pp. 193–205.
- [28] Porté-Agel, F. et al. “Large-eddy simulation of atmospheric boundary layer flow through wind turbines and wind farms”. In: *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* 99 (2011), pp. 154–168.
- [29] Wu, Y. T. and Porté-Agel, F. “Atmospheric turbulence effects on wind-turbine wakes: an LES study”. In: *Energies* 5 (2012), pp. 5340–5362.
- [30] Niayifar, Amin and Porté-Agel, Fernando. “Analytical modeling of wind farms: a new approach for power prediction”. In: *Energies* 9.9 (Sept. 2016), p. 741. DOI: 10.3390/en9090741. URL: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en9090741>.
- [31] Fuertes, Fernando Carbajo, Markfort, Corey D., and Porté-Agel, Fernando. “Wind Turbine Wake Characterization with Nacelle-Mounted Wind Lidars for Analytical Wake Model Validation”. In: *Remote Sensing* 10.5 (Apr. 2018), p. 668. DOI: 10.3390/rs10050668. URL: <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10050668>.
- [32] Ishihara, Takeshi and Qian, Guo-Wei. “A new Gaussian-based analytical wake model for wind turbines considering ambient turbulence intensities and thrust coefficient effects”. In: *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* 177 (May 2018), pp. 275–292. DOI: 10.1016/j.jweia.2018.04.010. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jweia.2018.04.010>.
- [33] Blondel, Frédéric and Cathelain, Marie. “An alternative form of the super-Gaussian wind turbine wake model”. In: *Wind energy science* 5.3 (Sept. 2020), pp. 1225–1236. DOI: 10.5194/wes-5-1225-2020. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-5-1225-2020>.

- [34] Bartl, Jan and Sætran, Lars. “Blind test comparison of the performance and wake flow between two in-line wind turbines exposed to different turbulent inflow conditions”. In: *Wind energy science* 2.1 (Feb. 2017), pp. 55–76. DOI: 10.5194/wes-2-55-2017. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-2-55-2017>.
- [35] Göçmen, Tuhfe et al. “Wind turbine wake models developed at the technical university of Denmark: A review”. In: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 60 (Feb. 2016), pp. 752–769. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.01.113. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.01.113>.
- [36] Ott, Søren and Nielsen, Morten. *Developments of the offshore wind turbine wake model Fuga*. Tech. rep. E-0046. DTU Wind Energy, 2014. URL: <https://orbit.dtu.dk/en/publications/4a0a6f81-ce21-42c8-bfde-3694d303d5e0>.
- [37] Gomez, Miguel Sanchez et al. “Investigating the physical mechanisms that modify wind plant blockage in stable boundary layers”. In: *Wind energy science* 8.7 (July 2023), pp. 1049–1069. DOI: 10.5194/wes-8-1049-2023. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-8-1049-2023>.
- [38] Habenicht, G. “Offshore Wake Modelling”. In: *Renewable UK Offshore Wind*. Presentation. RES.
- [39] Flaszynski, Pawel et al. “Numerical simulations for a parametric study of blockage effect on offshore wind farms”. In: *Wind Energy* 27.1 (Nov. 2023), pp. 53–74. DOI: 10.1002/we.2878. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.2878>.
- [40] Bleeg, James et al. “Wind farm blockage and the consequences of neglecting its impact on energy production”. In: *Energies* 11.6 (June 2018), p. 1609. DOI: 10.3390/en11061609. URL: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11061609>.
- [41] Sebastiani, Alessandro et al. “Data analysis and simulation of the Lillgrund wind farm”. In: *Wind Energy* 24.6 (Nov. 2020), pp. 634–648. DOI: 10.1002/we.2594. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.2594>.
- [42] Schneemann, Jörg et al. “Offshore wind farm global blockage measured with scanning lidar”. In: *Wind energy science* 6.2 (Apr. 2021), pp. 521–538. DOI: 10.5194/wes-6-521-2021. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-6-521-2021>.
- [43] Centurelli, G. et al. “Evaluating global blockage engineering parametrizations with LES”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2107.04265* (2021).
- [44] Allaerts, Dries and Meyers, Johan. “Boundary-layer development and gravity waves in conventionally neutral wind farms”. In: *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* 814 (Feb. 2017), pp. 95–130. DOI: 10.1017/jfm.2017.11. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2017.11>.
- [45] Wu, Ka and Porté-Agel, Fernando. “Flow adjustment inside and around large Finite-Size wind farms”. In: *Energies* 10.12 (Dec. 2017), p. 2164. DOI: 10.3390/en10122164. URL: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en10122164>.

- [46] Smith, Ronald B. “Interacting mountain waves and boundary layers”. In: *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences* 64.2 (Feb. 2007), pp. 594–607. DOI: 10.1175/jas3836.1. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1175/jas3836.1>.
- [47] Smith, R. B. “Gravity wave effects on wind farm efficiency”. In: *Wind Energy* 13.5 (Dec. 2009), pp. 449–458. DOI: 10.1002/we.366. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.366>.
- [48] Allaerts, Dries and Meyers, Johan. “Sensitivity and feedback of wind-farm-induced gravity waves”. In: *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* 862 (Jan. 2019), pp. 990–1028. DOI: 10.1017/jfm.2018.969. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2018.969>.
- [49] Lanzilao, L. and Meyers, J. “A parametric large-eddy simulation study of wind-farm blockage and gravity waves in conventionally neutral boundary layers”. In: *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* 979 (Jan. 2024). DOI: 10.1017/jfm.2023.1088. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2023.1088>.
- [50] Strickland, Jessica M.I., Gadde, Srinidhi N., and Stevens, Richard J.A.M. “Wind farm blockage in a stable atmospheric boundary layer”. In: *Renewable Energy* 197 (July 2022), pp. 50–58. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2022.07.108. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.07.108>.
- [51] RWE and Technical University of Denmark (RISØ) and DTU Wind Energy and TNO and Fraunhofer-IWES and Carbon Trust. “OWA GLOBE: Achieving industry Consensus on the global blockage effect in Offshore wind”. In: *WindEurope Technology Workshop Dublin*. 2024, pp. 2–22. URL: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/384562945>.
- [52] Stevens, Richard J. A. M., Gayme, Dennice F., and Meneveau, Charles. “Coupled wake boundary layer model of wind-farms”. In: *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy* 7.2 (Mar. 2015). DOI: 10.1063/1.4915287. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4915287>.
- [53] Calaf, Marc, Meneveau, Charles, and Meyers, Johan. “Large eddy simulation study of fully developed wind-turbine array boundary layers”. In: *Physics of Fluids* 22.1 (Jan. 2010). DOI: 10.1063/1.3291077. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3291077>.
- [54] Forsting, Alexander Meyer. “Shallow Layer Modelling”. Unpublished internal document, DTU Wind. 2025.
- [55] Pedersen, Mikael Mortensen and Hasager, Charlotte Bay. “PyWake: Engineering wind farm wake modeling in Python”. In: *Wind Energy Science* 6.3 (2021), pp. 775–794. DOI: 10.5194/wes-6-775-2021.
- [56] Ferrero, Enrico, Massabò, Dario, and Richiardone, Roberto. “Climatology of the Brunt–Väisälä frequency over Milan, Italy”. In: *Atmospheric Research* 76.1–4 (2005), pp. 356–372. DOI: 10.1016/j.atmosres.2004.11.016.

Appendix: Tools and Writing Aids

This thesis builds upon DTU's in-house MSC model, implemented in Python 3. Meteorological input data used for model initialization and analysis were provided by DTU and include lidar, met mast, and buoy-based observations from the GLOBE campaign. SCADA data from the Amrumbank West and Nordsee Ost wind farms were made available by RWE for research use. Publicly accessible datasets, including ERA5 reanalysis and WRF model outputs, were used to supplement the characterization of atmospheric conditions.

The document was written entirely in LaTeX, with all figures formatted and styled using native LaTeX plotting libraries.

I used OpenAI's ChatGPT as a support tool throughout this thesis, primarily to help structure Python code and improve the clarity of written language. Its use was limited to enhancing my workflow and organization; all scientific reasoning, implementation, and conclusions are entirely my own, informed by the sources cited in the references.